

**Optimization of Chitinase Production by *Bacillus* sp. B26 and
Its Antifungal Activity**

Edy Kurniawan

**A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of
Master of Science in Applied Biology
Prince of Songkla University
2019
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Thesis Title Optimization of Chitinase Production by *Bacillus* sp. B26 and Its Antifungal Activity
Author Mr. Edy Kurniawan
Major Program Applied Biology

Major Advisor

.....
(Dr. Somrak Panphon)

Examining Committee

.....Chairperson
(Asst. Prof. Dr. Jaruwan Maneesri)

Co-advisor

.....
(Asst. Prof. Dr. Montira Leelakriangsak)

.....
(Dr. Somrak Panphon)

.....
(Asst. Prof. Dr. Montira Leelakriangsak)

.....
(Asst. Prof. Dr. Walairat Bourchookarn)

.....
(Asst. Prof. Dr. Chaiwat Bandaiphet)

The Graduate School, Prince of Songkla University, has approved this thesis as partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Master of Science Degree in Applied biology

.....
(Prof. Dr. Damrongsak Faroongsarng)
Dean of Graduate School

This is to certify that the work here submitted is the result of the candidate's own investigations. Due acknowledgment has been made of any assistance received.

.....Signature
(Dr. Somrak Panphon)
Major Advisor

.....Signature
(Edy Kurniawan)
Candidate

I hereby certify that this work has not been accepted in substance for any degree and is not being currently submitted in candidature for any degree.

.....Signature
(Mr. Edy Kurniawan)
Candidate

ชื่อวิทยานิพนธ์	สภาวะที่เหมาะสมในการผลิตไคตินเนส โดย <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26 และฤทธิ์ยับยั้งเชื้อรา
ผู้เขียน	Mr. Edy Kurniawan
สาขาวิชา	ชีววิทยาประยุกต์
ปีการศึกษา	2561

บทคัดย่อ

การศึกษานี้เป็นการคัดเลือก *Bacillus* species ที่ได้คัดแยกจากตัวอย่างทางทะเล สำหรับการผลิตไคตินเนส และจัดจำแนกสายพันธุ์แบคทีเรียที่คัดเลือกได้ หลังจากนั้นศึกษาสภาวะที่เหมาะสมของพารามิเตอร์ ๆ ที่เกี่ยวข้องกับการหมักสำหรับการผลิตไคตินเนสโดยแบคทีเรียที่คัดเลือกได้ และทดสอบฤทธิ์ยับยั้งเชื้อรา แบคทีเรีย *Bacillus* จำนวนทั้งหมด 83 ไอโซเลต พบว่ามีจำนวน 14 ไอโซเลตสามารถผลิตไคตินเนสได้โดยพิจารณาจากการสร้างวงใสรอบ ๆ โคลินี้ บนอาหาร colloidal chitin agar แบคทีเรียที่มีค่าดัชนีการสร้างไคตินเนส (chitinolytic index) สูงสุดจำนวน 5 ไอโซเลต นำมาทดสอบฤทธิ์การเป็นปฏิปักษ์ต่อเชื้อราก่อโรค ผลการทดลองพบว่า ไอโซเลต B26 มีฤทธิ์ในการยับยั้งเชื้อรา *Alternaria alternata* TISTR 3435, *Fusarium solani* TISTR 3436, *Mucor ruber* TISTR 3006, และ *Penicillium chrysogenum* TISTR 3554 โดยมีการยับยั้งเชื้อราเท่ากับ 74.51%, 69.49%, 30.95% และ 46.51 % ตามลำดับ นำแบคทีเรียทั้ง 5 ไอโซเลตนำมาทดสอบความสามารถในการผลิตไคตินเนส ในอาหารเหลว colloidal chitin broth medium พบว่า ไอโซเลต B26 ผลิตไคตินเนสที่มีฤทธิ์ในการยับยั้งเชื้อรา *Fusarium solani* TISTR 3436 (44.5%) และ *Penicillium chrysogenum* TISTR 3554 (34.76%) ดังนั้นจึงได้คัดเลือก *Bacillus* sp. B26 ศึกษาคุณลักษณะของเชื้อและศึกษาสภาวะที่เหมาะสมในการผลิตเอนไซม์

Bacillus sp. B26 สามารถผลิต urease, catalase ย่อยสลายแป้ง และเคซีน แต่ไม่สามารถใช้ซิเตรต ให้ผลลบในการทดสอบออกซิเดส (oxidase test) ผลิตกรดจากการหมักน้ำตาลอราบินอส แล็กโตส มอลโตส กลูโคส ซูโครส กาแลกโตส แมนนิทอล และ ฟรุคโตส สามารถเจริญได้ในอาหารที่มี NaCl 0-5% โดยมีสภาวะที่เหมาะสม 2% pH 7-8 ที่ 37°C จากวิเคราะห์โดยใช้ 16S rRNA gene sequence พบว่า *Bacillus* sp. B26 มีความคล้ายคลึง (99%) กับเชื้อ *Bacillus paramycooides*

สภาวะที่เหมาะสมในการโคติเนสในสภาพอาหารเหลวโดย *Bacillus* sp. B26 พบว่าอาหารเหลวที่เหมาะสมมีองค์ประกอบดังนี้ ผงแกนในหมึก (squid pen powder) 2 % sodium nitrate 0.5 % สำหรับใช้เป็นแหล่งไนโตรเจนเสริม เกลือ NaCl 2 % ในอาหารที่มีองค์ประกอบ yeast extract 0.05%, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ 0.1% , $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.03%, และ KH_2PO_4 0.136 % พีเอชเริ่มต้น 7 ภายใต้สภาวะที่เหมาะสม *Bacillus* sp. B26 ผลิตโคติเนส มีแอกติวิตี้ 6.52 U/mL/h ในระยะเวลา 72 ชั่วโมง ผลได้ของโคติเนส (yield) เป็น 2.83 เท่า เมื่อเปรียบเทียบกับอาหารเลี้ยงเชื้อที่มีองค์ประกอบของผงแกนในหมึกก่อนการศึกษาสภาวะที่เหมาะสม นำสารละลายเอนไซม์โคติเนสที่ได้มาศึกษาฤทธิ์ยับยั้งเชื้อราชนิดต่าง ๆ พบว่าเอนไซม์โคติเนสมีประสิทธิภาพในการยับยั้งการเจริญของเส้นใยเชื้อรา *F. solani* TISTR 3436 (83.39%) และ *P. chrysogenum* TISTR 3554 (80.12%)

คำสำคัญ : สภาวะที่เหมาะสม, *Bacillus* spp. , *Bacillus paramycoides*, โคติเนสยับยั้งเชื้อรา

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Author	Mr. Edy Kurniawan
Major Program	Applied biology
Academic Year	2018

ABSTRACT

This study was carried out on the screening of *Bacillus* species isolated from marine samples for the production of chitinase and identification of the selected strain. Then fermentation parameters influencing chitinase production by the selected strain were optimized and tested its antifungal activity. Out of 83 *Bacillus* isolates, 14 bacterial isolates found producing chitinase characterized by clear inhibition around bacterial colonies on the colloidal chitin agar plate. Based on the chitinolytic index, five isolates were selected and tested for their antagonistic activity against pathogenic fungi. The results showed that the *Bacillus* sp. B26 had an antagonistic effect on *Alternaria alternata* TISTR 3435, *Fusarium solani* TISTR 3436, *Mucor ruber* TISTR 3006, and *Penicillium chrysogenum* TISTR 3554 with the percentage inhibition of 74.51, 69.49, 30.95, and 46.51, respectively. Five isolates were then tested for their ability to produce chitinase in the colloidal chitin broth medium. It was found that the *Bacillus* sp. B26 produced chitinase showing inhibiting activity against *Fusarium solani* TISTR 3436 (44.5%) and *Penicillium chrysogenum* TISTR 3554 (34.76%). Finally, *Bacillus* sp. B26 was selected for the characterization and optimization process of enzyme production.

Bacillus sp. B26 showed positive results for urease production, catalase test, starch hydrolysis, and casein hydrolysis but negative results with citrate utilization, oxidase test, and Voges-Proskauer reaction. It produced acids by fermentation of sugar such as arabinose, lactose, maltose, glucose, sucrose, galactose, mannitol, and fructose. *Bacillus* sp. B26 could grow in medium containing 0-5 % NaCl with optimum at 2% NaCl, pH 7-8, at 37°C. Based on the 16S rRNA gene sequence, *Bacillus* sp. B26 had sequence similarity (99%) with *Bacillus paramycooides*. The composition of an optimized medium for the production of chitinase by *Bacillus* sp. B26 was found to be 2% of squid pen powder, 0.5% of sodium nitrate as the best additional nitrogen source

and 2% of NaCl in the basal medium containing 0.05% of yeast extract, 0.1% of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, 0.03% of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.136% of KH_2PO_4 with initial medium pH 7. Under the optimized conditions, *Bacillus* sp. B26 gave a maximum chitinase activity of 6.52 U/mL/h, which was achieved after 72 h of incubation. The yield of 2.83-fold was observed as compared to the unoptimized basal medium with squid pen powder as a substrate. Antifungal activity of the obtained crude chitinase was tested against several fungal strains. It was found that the crude chitinase proved to be more effective in inhibiting the mycelial growth of *F. solani* TISTR 3436 (83.39%) and *P. chrysogenum* TISTR 3554 (80.12%).

Keywords: Optimization, *Bacillus* spp., *Bacillus paramycooides*, antifungal chitinase

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

First of all, I want to thank Allah SWT, God Almighty for bestowing mercy and grace and not forgetting greetings to His messenger prophet Muhammad SAW. The biggest thank you, I want to convey to my great advisor, Dr. Somrak Panphon, for guidance, dedication, and constructive input for my research. She always encouraged me to work, pay attention to me in life, and provide useful criticism in maintaining my progress on schedule. Other than that, as part of her team, I am also ready to become a master in the field of microbiology, which will be useful for academics and careers in the future.

I want to convey my gratitude to Asst. Montira Leelakriangsak, my advisor in consultation, especially in research design and evaluation. Every time I experience a deadlock, she is willing to support the idea so that my progress continues to grow. She also helped deductively in correcting my manuscript. I also thank other committees: Asst. Prof. Dr. Jaruwan Maneesri, Asst. Prof. Dr. Walairat Bourchookarn for constructive suggestions and input on the progress of thesis writing so that I can complete the thesis. And also for Asst. Prof. Dr. Chaiwat Bandaipheth as the external examiner who has provided input in academic writing in English. I sincerely thank Dr. Waewruedee Waewthongrak, the Committee chair of Applied Biology, who has given me knowledge and experience about laboratory use.

I want to express my deepest gratitude to the Postgraduate School and the Faculty of Science and Technology, Prince of Songkla University, for their scholarship and grant research during a master's degree. My sincere and profound gratitude is given to lecturers and staff in the Biology Division, Department of Science, for facilitating and providing suggestions for the progress of the research results. Without their help, there is no doubt that I cannot complete the project and my master's degree.

Thank you, I convey to Ms. Sukallaya Hemmanee, who always helps me whenever I have a problem in the laboratory, especially regarding work safety issues in a chemical laboratory. And I do not forget to thank all the Master students in the Biology Division who have worked together in the laboratory and have provided many

constructive inputs in every difficulty that I face. Thanks are also given to the Indonesian Student Association in Thailand who have jointly created an atmosphere and are full of kinship. Mainly, I thank my wife, Ms. Amney, which has provided a lot of motivation, ideas, and advice all the time so that my research and thesis can be completed. The most important, I want to present this thesis to my beloved family. With their love, I can motivate myself to do my best so that the thesis can be completed properly.

Edy Kurniawan

TABLE OF CONTENT

Title	Page
บทคัดย่อ	v
ABSTRACT.....	vii
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	xi
LIST OF TABLES	xiv
LIST OF FIGURES	xvi
CHAPTER 1	1
INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background and rationale	1
1.2 Objectives of the research.....	2
1.3 Expected advantages.....	3
CHAPTER 2	4
LITERATURE REVIEW	4
2.1 Shellfish waste	4
2.2 Structure of chitin	5
2.3 Chitinases.....	6
2.4 Classification of chitinases	7
2.5 Bacterial chitinase.....	9
2.6 Production of chitinase	11
2.7 Submerged fermentation system.....	11
2.8 Optimization of the cultural process for chitinase production.....	12
2.8.1 Carbon source and concentration.....	12
2.8.2 Additional carbon source	13
2.8.3 Nitrogen sources and concentration.....	14
2.8.4 pH.....	15
2.8.5 Incubation period	16
2.8.6 NaCl	17
2.8.7 Agitation speed	17
2.9 Applications of bacterial chitinases	18
2.9.1 Antifungal agent.....	18
2.9.2 Chitinase as nematicidal agent.....	21

2.9.3	Chitinase as an insecticidal agent	21
2.9.4	Chitinase for isolation of protoplast.....	23
CHAPTER 3		24
METHODOLOGY		24
3.1	Materials	24
3.1.1	Chitinous waste.....	24
3.1.2	Microorganism.....	24
3.1.3	Culture media and chemicals	24
3.2	Instruments.....	25
3.3	Experiment.....	26
3.3.1	Preparation of bacteria	26
3.3.2	Preparation of fungi	26
3.3.3	Preparation of colloidal chitin.....	26
3.3.4	Preparation of chitin substrates	26
3.3.5	Primary screening and selection of chitinase producing bacteria	27
3.3.6	Screening of antagonistic activity of chitinolytic bacteria against pathogenic fungi.....	27
3.3.7	Secondary screening of chitinase producing bacteria.....	28
3.3.8	Chitinase activity assay.....	28
3.3.9	Identification of the selected chitinolytic <i>Bacillus</i> sp. strain B26	29
3.3.10	Optimization of chitinase production.....	30
3.3.10.1	Effect of different substrates and concentrations on chitinase production.....	30
3.3.10.2	Effect of additional carbon source and concentration on chitinase production	30
3.3.10.3	Effect of nitrogen sources and concentrations on chitinase production.....	31
3.3.10.4	Effect the NaCl concentrations on chitinase production	31
3.3.10.5	Effect of initial pH of a medium on chitinase production.....	31
3.3.10.6	Effect of incubation time on chitinase production	32
3.3.11	Evaluation of the antifungal activity of crude chitinase	32
3.4	Data analysis	33

CHAPTER 4	34
RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	34
4.1 Primary screening and selection of chitinase producing bacteria.....	34
4.2 Screening of antagonistic activity of chitinolytic bacteria against pathogenic fungi.....	37
4.3 Secondary screening of chitinase producing bacteria.....	39
4.4 Identification of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26	40
4.5 Analysis of DNA sequences	43
4.6 Optimization of chitinase production.....	44
4.6.1 Effect of different substrates on chitinase activity and growth of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26.....	44
4.6.2 Effect of substrate concentration on chitinase activity and growth of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26.....	46
4.6.3 Effect of additional carbon sources on chitinase production and growth of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26.....	47
4.6.4 Effect of nitrogen source on chitinase production and growth of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26.....	49
4.6.5 Effect of nitrogen source concentrations on chitinase activity and growth of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26.....	50
4.6.6 Effect of NaCl concentrations on chitinase production	51
4.6.7 Effect of initial pH of the medium on chitinase production	53
4.6.8 Effect of incubation time on chitinase production.....	54
4.7 Antifungal activity of crude chitinase after the optimized condition	55
CHAPTER 5	58
CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION.....	58
5.1 Conclusion	58
5.2 Recommendation	59
APPENDIX A.....	82
APPENDIX B	85
APPENDIX C	91
VITAE.....	105

LIST OF TABLES

Table	Page
Table 1 Percentage of chitin content to the body mass of crustacean.....	4
Table 2 Proximate composition percentage of the dry basis of crustacean shell wastes	5
Table 3 The properties of chitinase based on the amino acid sequence of the GH-18 module.....	9
Table 4 Source of chitinase producing microorganisms	10
Table 5 Carbon sources for chitinase production.....	12
Table 6 Additional carbon sources and concentration for chitinase production by bacteria.....	13
Table 7 Nitrogen sources and concentration for chitinase production by bacteria	14
Table 8 Suitable initial pH of the medium for chitinase production by bacteria	15
Table 9 Incubation period for chitinase production by bacteria.....	16
Table 10 NaCl concentration for chitinase production by bacteria.....	17
Table 11 Agitation speed for chitinase production by bacteria.....	18
Table 12 Bacterial agents for biocontrol of fungal plant pathogens	19
Table 13 Bacterial chitinase as nematocidal agent	21
Table 14 Bacterial chitinase that acts as an insecticidal agent	22
Table 15 Bacterial chitinase used for isolation of protoplast	23
Table 16 Chitinolytic activity of <i>Bacillus</i> isolates	35
Table 17 Antagonistic activity of chitinolytic <i>Bacillus</i> isolates against various pathogenic fungi	37
Table 18 Chitinase activity and growth of the selected <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26 after incubation for 72 hours.....	39
Table 19 Antifungal activity of crude chitinase of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26 against various pathogenic fungi	40
Table 20 Characterization of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26.....	41
Table 21 Antagonistic activity of crude chitinase after optimization against pathogenic fungi.....	56
Table 22 Primary screening of chitinase producing bacteria	91

Table 23 Antagonistic activity of chitinolytic bacteria against pathogenic fungi.....	92
Table 24 Chitinase activity of <i>Bacillus</i> spp. in secondary screening	96
Table 25 Antifungal activity of crude chitinase of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26 against pathogenic fungi	97
Table 26 Effect of chitin source on chitinase production by <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26	98
Table 27 Effect of chitin source concentration on chitinase production by <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26	98
Table 28 Effect of additional carbon source on chitinase production by <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26	99
Table 29 Effect of nitrogen source on chitinase production by <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26.....	99
Table 30 Effect of nitrogen source concentration on chitinase production by <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26	100
Table 31 Effect of NaCl concentration on chitinase production by <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26	100
Table 32 Effect of initial pH of medium on chitinase production by <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26	101
Table 33 Effect of incubation on chitinase production by <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26.....	101
Table 34 Antifungal activity of optimization crude chitinase of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26 ...	102

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure	Page
Figure 1 (a) Chemical structure of chitin. The gray box indicates one N acetylglucosamine sub-unit of the chitin chain. (b) The two major types of chitin characterized by an anti-parallel (α -chitin) or parallel (β -chitin) arrangement of the chains.	6
Figure 2 Action of chitinolytic enzymes on chitin.	8
Figure 3 The chitinous waste powder after passed through a 120 mesh (a) shrimp shell powder (b) crab shell powder, and (c) squid pen powder.	27
Figure 4 Plate assay showing the chitinase activity of the <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26 on colloidal chitin agar after 5 days at 30°C.	34
Figure 5 Distribution of chitinolytic <i>Bacillus</i> spp. from marine samples.	35
Figure 6 PCR amplification of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26.	44
Figure 7 Effect of substrate on chitinase production and growth of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).	46
Figure 8 Effect of squid pen powder concentration on chitinase production and growth of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).	47
Figure 9 Effect of additional carbon source on chitinase production and growth of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).	48
Figure 10 Effect of nitrogen sources on chitinase production and growth of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).	50

- Figure 11** Effect of sodium nitrate concentration on chitinase production and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).....51
- Figure 12** Effect of NaCl concentration on chitinase production and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).....52
- Figure 13** Effect of initial pH of the medium on chitinase production and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).....54
- Figure 14** Effect of incubation time on chitinase production and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation.....55
- Figure 15** Antifungal activity of chitinase produced by *Bacillus* sp. B26 against (A) *Fusarium solani* TISTR 3436 and (B) *Penicillium chrysogenum* TISTR 3554. (1) 5-min-boiled crude chitinase, (2) 2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of amphotericin B (3) Crude chitinase, and (4) uninoculated crude enzyme.....56
- Figure 16** Standard curve of N-acetylglucosamine (NAG) solution and equation of the straight line.....89

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and rationale

Marine products, including shrimp, crab, and squid, have a reasonably high market demand globally. The global impact of this scenario is the increasing demand for crustacean products that produce biowaste from the seafood industry. Disposal of large amounts of biowaste to coastal areas has contributed to environmental pollution, which impacts on the ecosystem (Remoundou and Koundouri, 2009). Besides that, by removing valuable byproducts without being recycled and utilized, the seafood industry loses the foremost opportunity to get significant products, for example, chitin, chitosan, and N-acetylglucosamine (Suresh *et al.*, 2011a). Global production in 2016 of crustacean about 7.9 million tonnes of shellfish is produced globally, about 7 million tonnes in Asia alone (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2018). Therefore, the compelling utilization of biowaste has a significant role not just in ecological support but also in increasing economic value through by-products (Bhaskar *et al.*, 2010). At this point, bioconversion of chitin into value-added products such as N-acetylglucosamine and chitosan has been proposed as an option to effective biowaste treatment and is well received because it is useful and environmentally friendly in its utilization (Suresh *et al.*, 2011b).

Chitinase is an enzyme that can degrade chitin polymer. Chitin can be found in different life forms, including crustaceans, mollusks, insects, and fungi (Rathore and Gupta, 2015). Chitinase is now widely used in the agricultural industry, even in recent years (Hamid *et al.*, 2013). Nevertheless, the production of microbial extracellular chitinases have gotten much attention as of late because of their potential use in processing biowaste crustaceans, production of N-Acetylglucosamine and chitooligosaccharides (Suresh *et al.*, 2011a), single-cell protein (Patil, and Jadhav, 2014), isolation of protoplasts (Patil and Jadhav, 2015), control of fungi (Gurav *et al.*, 2017), insect (Wang *et al.*, 2013a), and mosquito (Halder *et al.*, 2012). Apart from its significance in the industrial and environmental fields, inversely proportional to low chitinase activity and stability and high production costs, which limit commercial

exploitation (Suresh and Kumar 2012). great efforts are being investigated by researchers in utilizing new microbial species as well as various bioprocesses for effective and efficient production of enzymes (Nigam, 2013). In this context, submerged fermentation (SmF) has favorable in process control, and recovery of enzymes is moderately simple contrasted with SSF (Karthik *et al.*, 2017). The use of cheap raw materials and relatively easy processes are the advantages of SSF, although there are few problems with temperature control, pH, and substrate sterilization. (Matsumoto *et al.*, 2004).

Marine microbes have recently emerged as new sources in industrial enzymes (Dumorné and Severe, 2018). The facts show that there is no accumulation of chitin substrate on the seabed (Suginta *et al.*, 2013). This data shows that the chitin substrate is degraded by naturally occurring bioconversion processes carried out by chitinolytic marine bacteria (Claudiana *et al.*, 2011). Marine microbial have been recognized as potential sources of chitinase (Austin, 1988), and they have been involved in chitin degradation in marine ecosystems (Claudiana *et al.*, 2011). Some researchers also have to isolate, purify, and characterize chitinase marine bacteria including *Bacillus subtilis* (Senol *et al.*, 2014), *Bacillus atrophaeus* (Anuradha and Revathi, 2017), *PaeniBacillus barengoltzii* (Yang *et al.*, 2016), and *Streptomyces vinaceusdrappus* (Yandigeri *et al.*, 2015). However, available information about process parameters that affect chitinase production and antimicrobial activity of marine bacteria during bioprocess is rather small. In this context, the research was conducted to effectively utilize marine bacteria for bioconversion of biowaste together with chitinase production and antifungal activity.

1.2 Objectives of the research

The objectives of this study were described as:

1. To screen chitinase-producing *Bacillus* isolates isolated from marine samples.
2. To identify the selected chitinolytic *Bacillus* sp.
3. To optimize the culture medium and conditions for the maximum production of chitinase by the selected *Bacillus* strain in submerged fermentation using ‘one factor at a time’ method.
4. To examine the antifungal activity of crude chitinase against fungi.

1.3 Expected advantages

1. Obtaining *Bacillus* sp. for the production of chitinase using marine chitin waste under submerged fermentation.
2. It is hoped that the research will be able to find the optimum medium composition and conditions for bacterial fermentation in producing abundant crude chitinase. So it is expected to reduce production costs through the use of crustacean waste as the primary substrate.
3. Crude chitinase is expected to have the ability as an antifungal in plant pathogenic fungi so that it will be a sustainable solution in agriculture

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Shellfish waste

Currently, crustaceans are the leading producers of chitin available for industrial management processes. Among the most abundant sources of chitin are shellfish and squid, which have been harvested around 7.9 million tons in 2016 (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2018). Chitin composition in crustacean ranges from 2% to 12% of all body mass (Table 1).

chitin, protein, minerals, and carotene in shell waste vary greatly depending on processing, species, parts of the organism, and stages of the reproductive cycle (Sewvandi and Adikary, 2012).

Table 1 Percentage of chitin content to the body mass of crustacean

Crustacean order	Chitin content, as percentage body mass of crustacean	
	Freshwater	Seawater
Cladocera	4.9	12.2
Anostraca	2.2	1.5
Copepoda	12.4	5.8
Amphipoda	-	7.3
Decapoda	-	8.8

Source: Cauchie (1997)

The most exploited sources of chitin are shrimp and crabs (Table 2). The dried waste content of chitin, which has been processed in krill ranges 34 to 49% higher than shrimp which ranges from 14 to 42% and crabs ranging from 13 to 26%.

Table 2 Proximate composition percentage of the dry basis of crustacean shell wastes

Chitin source	Protein	Chitin	Ash	Lipids
Crab: <i>Callinectes sapidus</i>	25.1	13.52	58.6	2.1
<i>Chionoecetes opilio</i>	29.2	26.6	40.6	1.3
Shrimp: <i>Pandalus borealis</i>	41.9	17.0	34.2	5.2
<i>Crangon crangon</i>	40.6	17.8	27.5	9.9
<i>Penaeus monodon</i>	47.4	40.4	23.0	1.3
Crawfish: <i>Procambarus clarkii</i>	29.8	13.2	46.6	5.6
Krill: <i>Euphausia superba</i>	41.0	24.0	23.0	11.6
Prawn	61.6	33.0	29.4	1.4

Source: Synowiecki and Al-Khateeb (2000)

2.2 Structure of chitin

Chitin is a polysaccharide composed of N-acetylglucosamine residues in the beta chain and has a monomer in the form of a glucose molecule with branches containing nitrogen. Chitin is the most abundant polymer in the sea. Whereas in abundance on earth, Chitin is second only to cellulose. This is because chitin can be found in various eukaryotic organisms, including insects, mollusks, crustaceans, fungi, algae, and protists (Elieh-Ali-Komi and Hamblin, 2016). Each polymer chain generally consists of 2000 to 5000 N-Acetyl-D-Glucosamine monomer units (2-acetamido-2-deoxy-D-Glucose), which adhere to the bond of β (1.4) glucose (Synowiecki and Al-Khateeb, 2003). There are α -chitin, β -chitin, and γ -chitin forms of chitin (Figure 1). Alpha chitins are composed of alternating antiparallel polysaccharide strands mostly found in the crustacean. The type of beta-chitin has polymer chains arranged in parallel and found as a skeletal composer in squid. In gamma chitin, each fibril is composed of three chains; the two chains are arranged parallel, and the third chain of the antiparallel (Svitil *et al.*, 1997).

Figure 1 (a) Chemical structure of chitin. The gray box indicates one N acetylglucosamine sub-unit of the chitin chain. (b) Two types of chitin characterized by an anti-parallel (α -chitin) or parallel (β -chitin) arrangement of the chains.

Source: Seidl (2008)

The minerals contained in the shell can be removed by acidification. Chitin can be dissolved in HCl, H₂SO₄, H₃PO₄ concentrated, dichloroacetic acid (DCA), trichloroacetic acid (TCA), and formic acids. The rate of solubilization of β -chitin is higher than that of α -chitin. Besides, this polysaccharide is also soluble in hot, the concentrated solution of some neutral salts, hexafluoroisopropanol (HFIP), and hexafluoroacetone (Synowiecki and Al-Khateeb, 2003).

2.3 Chitinases

Chitinase (EC 3.2.2.14) is an enzyme that can catalyze chitin degradation reactions by cutting the glycosidic bond between the N-acetylglucosamine residue (chitin-forming monomer) (Bhattacharya *et al.*, 2007), which was used in many biotechnological fields as a biologically functional material (Han *et al.*, 2008). Chitinases are mainly found in plants, bacteria, fungi, insects, animals, and actinomycetes (Hamid *et al.*, 2013). Mostly, chitin containing organisms contain chitinase, which is required for the morphogenesis of cell walls and exoskeletons. However, some organisms do not contain chitin but produce chitinases, e.g., bacteria (Rathore and Gupta, 2015). The functions of chitinases in various organisms are diverse. Like yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, this enzyme is involved in cell division

and cell separation (Molon *et al.*, 2018). In the plant, chitinase secretion is caused by infections of chitin-enriched microbes (fungi, insects) or other injuries by plant defenses to protect them. Chitinase activity is promoted by fungal, bacterial, and viral infections since it is considered pathogen-related (PR) proteins. Fungal chitinases like bacterial chitinases have multiple functions as they play an essential role in the fungal development process, morphogenesis, and nutrition (Hamid *et al.*, 2013). In fish, it is usually a part of the digestive tract to degrade chitin (Ikeda *et al.*, 2017). In insects and crustaceans, chitinases are needed for partial degradation of the old cuticle (Chen *et al.*, 2014), while in humans, chitinases are involved in the modulate immune responses (Mack *et al.*, 2015).

2.4 Classification of chitinases

Classification of chitinase based on action mode is divided into three types, namely, exochitinase, endochitinase, and β -1,4-N-acetylglucosaminidase (Figure 2). Exochitinase is an enzyme that actively catalyzes the release of diacetylobiose units without the formation of a monosaccharide unit or oligosaccharide. This enzyme only randomly cut the non-reduced end of the microfibril. Endochitinase (EC. 3.2.1.14) is an enzyme that works by cutting randomly β -1,4 bonds of internal parts of chitin microfibril. Short oligomer N-acetylglucosamine is the final product formed after cutting with low molecular weight. The products formed are soluble in water. β -1,4-N-acetylglucosaminidase (EC. 3.2.1.30) is a chitinolytic enzyme producer of GlcNAc monomers (Chen *et al.*, 2010).

Based on amino acid sequence similarity, they can be grouped into glycosyl hydrolase families (GH) 18, 19, and 20, which are structurally unrelated (Henrissat and Davies, 1997). The catalytic mechanism of chitinases family 18 involving substrate contributes to catalysis, which maintains the anomeric configuration of the product. Family 18 includes chitinase from bacteria, fungi, viruses, some from plants and animals (Matsumoto *et al.*, 2006). The catalytic mechanism of chitinases family 19 is a common acid-base mechanism that reverses the anomeric configuration of hydrolyzed NAG residues. Family 19 includes overall plant chitinase (Kasprzewska, 2003). Family 20 includes the β -N-acetylhexosaminidase from bacteria such as *Vibrio harveyi* and *Streptomyces* (Synowiecki and Al-Khateeb, 2003).

Figure 2 Action of chitinolytic enzymes on chitin

Source: Stoykov *et al.* (2015)

Based on the amino acid sequence of the GH-18 module, microbial chitinase is divided into three groups, namely, A, B, and C. The difference between the three groups in the architecture of the substrate-binding cleft, its catalytic activity (Exo vs. endo), and different carbohydrate-binding modules (CBM) (Hartl *et al.*, 2012). The presence of CBM in enzymes allows them to bind more tightly to the insoluble substrate to improve the process. The properties of the chitinase subgroups A-C are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3 The properties of chitinase based on the amino acid sequence of the GH-18 module

Sub-group	Molecular mass (kDa)	Substrate binding cleft	Mode of cleavage	Chitinase class	CBM	Location of CBM
A	40-60	Deep and narrow	Exo	Fungal/bacterial	-	-
B	30-50	Shallow and open	Endo	Fungal/plant	Varies among species	C-terminus
C	120-200	Deep and narrow	Exo (predicted)	Fungal/bacterial	CBM 18 and 50	N-terminus

CBM, Carbohydrate-binding module.

Source: Hartl *et al.* (2012)

2.5 Bacterial chitinase

Bacteria produce chitinases to supply carbon and nitrogen as sources of nutrients and energy. In bacterial chitinase, a chitin-binding domain either located in the enzyme's amino-terminal or carboxyl-terminal domains. It can hydrolyze GlcNAc-GlcNAc and GlcNAc-glucosamine linkages. Bacterial chitinase with 20-60 kDa molecular weight is active in a broad array of pH and temperatures, depending on the source of the isolates (Rathore and Gupta, 2015). Table 4 shows the source of chitinase producing microorganisms.

Table 4 Source of chitinase producing microorganisms (Published from 2014 onwards)

Microorganism	Source of isolation	Reference
<i>PaeniBacillus barengoltzii</i>	Seawater sample	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	Leaves and root rhizospheres	Senol <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp.	Coastal environmental samples	Karthik <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	Soil samples	Liang <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Laceyella putida</i>	Deep subseafloor core sediments	Shibasaki <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Pseudoalteromonas</i> sp. DL-6	Marine sediment samples	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>PaeniBacillus pasadenensis</i> NCIM 5434	Alkaline littoral soil of lake	Loni <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. CS495	Soil sample	Pradeep <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> LHH100	Wastewater samples	Laribi-Habchi <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Chitinibacter</i> sp. GC72	Pond mud	Gao <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Acinetobacter</i> ASK18	Marine waste	Krithika and Chellaram (2016)
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	Rubber tree	Tan <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> and <i>Bacillus atrophaeus</i>	Crustacean shells	Anuradha and Revathi (2017)
<i>Aeromonas veronii</i> B565	Aquaculture pond sediment	Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Chromobacterium</i> C61	Soil sample	Kim <i>et al.</i> (2014)

2.6 Production of chitinase

Fermentation technology plays a significant role in the field of biotechnology not only for the production of various enzymes, antibiotics, single-cell proteins, and different food products, but it also reduces the cost and time of production. Microorganisms are the primary sources for the production of chitinase because they have the shortest generation time, high yield conversion of substrates into the product, extraordinary versatility to environmental conditions, and simplicity in genetic manipulation and conditions of cultivation. Due to habitat diversity, microorganisms usually produce different types of chitinases, with different specificities regarding substrate utilization and also for optimum pH and temperature ranges (Gurung *et al.*, 2013).

2.7 Submerged fermentation system

Submerged Fermentation is a fermentation that involves water as a continuous phase of a cell's growth system or substrate, both carbon sources and minerals dissolved as particles in the liquid phase. According to Mussatto and Teixeira (2010), several characteristics make these systems attractive for the cultivation of microorganism and production of biological products, which include:

- i) The mixture of the medium is natural and allows uniform conditions for the growth of microorganisms.
- ii) Modification of the cultivation conditions like pH, dissolved oxygen, temperature, agitation, and nutrient concentration is effortless.
- iii) The temperature control is preferred by the high specific heat and thermal conductivity
- iv) Efficient technologies have been developed, with high-class automation, diversity, and equipment availability

Countless microorganism strains have been used in fermentation processes for the production of chitinase by submerged cultivation, including bacteria, yeasts, fungi, and algae (Beygmoradi and Homaei, 2017).

2.8 Optimization of the cultural process for chitinase production

Microbial chitinases are mostly intracellular inducible and greatly influenced by nutritional and physicochemical factors, such as carbon and nitrogen sources, pH, temperature, inorganic salts, agitation, metal ion, and incubation period (Cheba, 2017). The primary factor for the expression of chitinases activity has always been the type, and the form of chitin and the most inducing substrates are colloidal chitin, crystalline chitin, or shrimp or crab powder (Cheba, 2017).

Several studies on chitinases optimization have been reported earlier with the effect of different media components and production conditions on its secretion using the classical approach (one-factor-at-a-time” OFAT” method), which means changing one factor at a time while keeping others at a constant level (Irfan *et al.*, 2014).

2.8.1 Carbon source and concentration

Bacterial chitinase is inducible, and the existence of chitin in the production medium dramatically enhances the yield of chitinase. Chitin at a concentration of 1-1.5 percent contributes to maximum chitinase production (Karthik *et al.*, 2014). Some of the best carbon sources for chitinase production of bacteria are presented in Table 5.

Table 5 Carbon sources for chitinase production

Microorganism	Carbon source	Reference
<i>PaeniBacillus barengoltzii</i>	Colloidal chitin (1%)	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp.	Colloidal chitin (1.4%)	Karthik <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	Squid pen powder (1%)	Liang <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Laceyella putida</i>	N-acetyl glucosamine (GlcNAc) (0.5%)	Shibasaki <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Pseudoalteromonas</i> sp. DL-6	Colloidal chitin (0.5%)	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>PaeniBacillus pasadenensis</i> NCIM 5434	Colloidal chitin (0.8%)	Loni <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. CS495	Colloidal chitin (0.5%)	Pradeep <i>et al.</i> (2014)

Table 5 continued

Microorganism	Carbon source	Reference
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> strain LHH100	Colloidal chitin (1%)	Laribi-Habchi <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Chitinibacter</i> sp. GC72	crayfish shell powder (1%)	Gao <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> and <i>Bacillus atrophaeus</i>	Colloidal chitin (1%)	Anuradha and Revathi (2017)
<i>Vibrio alginolyticus</i> JN863235	Colloidal chitin (0.3%)	Ravikumar and Meignanalakshmi (2013)

2.8.2 Additional carbon source

Adding carbon sources other than chitin to the medium of production could have a blended impact. Table 6 shows the effect of an additional carbon source on chitinase production.

Table 6 Additional carbon sources and concentration for chitinase production by bacteria

Bacterial species	Carbon source	Effect of production	Reference
<i>BreviBacillus formosus</i> BISR-1	Glycerol (1%)	Increase	Meena <i>et al.</i> (2014a)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.R2	Glucose (0.5%)	Increase	Cheba <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>Streptomyces rubiginosus</i>	Xylose (2%)	Increase	Jha <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>Cohnella</i> sp. A01	Cellulose (1%)	Decrease	Aliabadi <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>Streptomyces pratensis</i> KLSL55	Fructose (1.52%)	Increase	Shivalee <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>PaeniBacillus</i> sp. BISR-047	Glycerol (0.1%)	Increase	Meena <i>et al.</i> (2014b)
<i>PaeniBacillus thermoaerophilus</i> TC22-2b	Lactose (0.3%)	Decrease	Ueda and Kurosawa (2015)

Table 6 continued

Bacterial species	Carbon source	Effect of production	Reference
<i>Citrobacter freundii</i> haritD11	Starch (1%)	Increase not significant	Meruvu and Donthireddy (2014)
<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i> and <i>Aeromonas punctata</i>	Starch (1%)	Increase	Saima <i>et al.</i> (2013)
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	Fructose (0.1%)	Decrease	Chakraborty <i>et al.</i> (2012)
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	Galactose (0.5%)	Increase	Gomaa (2012)
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	Lactose (0.5%)	Increase	Gomaa (2012)

2.8.3 Nitrogen sources and concentration

Nitrogen regulation is essential in industrial microbiology as it impacts the synthesis of enzymes engaged in both primary and secondary metabolisms. Many reviews are available on the effect of the supplementation of nitrogen sources on chitinase production of bacteria (Table 7).

Table 7 Nitrogen sources and concentration for chitinase production by bacteria

Bacterial species	Nitrogen source	Effect of production	Reference
<i>BreviBacillus formosus</i> BISR-1	Ammonium nitrate (0.3%)	Increase	Meena <i>et al.</i> (2014a)
<i>Streptomyces rubiginosus</i>	Peptone (2%)	Decrease	Jha <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>Cohnella</i> sp. A01	Ammonium nitrate (1%)	Decrease	Aliabadi <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>Streptomyces pratensis</i> KLSL55	Potassium nitrate (0.5%)	Increase	Shivalee <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>PaeniBacillus</i> sp. BISR-047	Ammonium sulfate (0.2%)	Increase	Meena <i>et al.</i> (2014b)

Table 7 continued

Bacterial species	Nitrogen source	Effect of production	Reference
<i>Citrobacter freundii</i> haritD11	Yeast extract (2.36%)	Increase	Meruvu and Donthireddy (2014)
<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i>	Malt extract (1%)	Decrease	Saima <i>et al.</i> (2013)
<i>Aeromonas punctata</i>	Yeast extract (1%)	Decrease	Saima <i>et al.</i> (2013)
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	Yeast extract (0.1%)	Increase	Chakraborty <i>et al.</i> (2012)
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> and <i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	Casein (0.5%)	Increase	Gomaa (2012)

2.8.4 pH

The pH plays a significant role in the production of chitinase. Generally, near-neutral pH of 6.0-8.0 is obtained in bacterial chitinase production. The optimum pH for chitinase production is different depending on the organisms. Many reports are available on the effects of the initial medium on chitinase production (Table 8).

Table 8 Suitable initial pH of the medium for chitinase production by bacteria

Bacterial species	Optimum pH	References
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. R2	7.5	Cheba <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>Streptomyces violaceusniger</i>	9	Nagpure <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Chitinolyticbacter meiyuanensis</i> SYBC-H1	8	Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>BreviBacillus formosus</i> BISR-1	5	Meena <i>et al.</i> (2014a)
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	7	Liang <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	5	Anuradha and Revathi (2017)

Table 8 continued

Bacterial species	Optimum pH	References
<i>Bacillus atrophaeus</i>	8	Anuradha and Revathi (2017)
<i>Serratia marcescens</i> SEN	9	Aggarwal <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Streptomyces anulatus</i> CS242	6	Mander <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>Streptomyces rubiginosus</i>	7	Jha <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>PaeniBacillus</i> sp. D3	7	Chrisnasari <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i>	8	Saima <i>et al.</i> (2013)
<i>Aeromonas punctate</i>	7	Saima <i>et al.</i> (2013)

2.8.5 Incubation period

The incubation period determines the time point for peak enzyme production. The reasons for reduced production of enzymes after extended incubation may be the depletion of nutrients, medium production of inhibitory chemicals and the result is the inactivation of the enzyme secretory machinery; or the enzyme's degradation itself. Most bacterial and fungal sources usually involve 48-96 hours for peak chitinase production (Karthik *et al.*, 2017). Table 9 shows the incubation period on some bacterial chitinase production.

Table 9 Incubation period for chitinase production by bacteria

Bacterial species	Optimum time (hour)	References
<i>Streptomyces rubiginosus</i>	72	Jha <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>Streptomyces pratensis</i> KLSL55	48	Shivalee <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>Bacillus pumilus</i> JUBCH08	72	Bhattacharya <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>Acinetobacter parvus</i> HANDI 309	24	Kim <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>Streptomyces albus</i> FS12	120	Santhi (2016)

2.8.6 NaCl

There are some bacterial chitinases, which are expressed in response to environmental stresses (i.e., high salt concentration). Marine bacterial typically exhibit a broad tolerance to salinity, while terrestrial bacteria are inhibited by higher salinity, especially their reproduction and spore germination. Table 10 shows the effect of NaCl on marine bacterial chitinase production.

Table 10 NaCl concentration for chitinase production by bacteria

Bacterial species	NaCl concentration	References
<i>Cohnella</i> sp. A01	0.17%	Aliabadi <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>Streptoallotecichus</i> sp. and <i>Nocardiopsis</i> sp.	0%	Vijayakumar <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Bacillus pumilus</i> SG2	0.5 M	Vahed <i>et al.</i> (2013)
<i>VirgiBacillus marismortui</i> M3-23 and <i>TerriBacillus halophilus</i>	0%	Essghaier <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Planococcus rifitoensis</i>	10%	Essghaier <i>et al.</i> (2010)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. R2	2.5%	Cheba <i>et al.</i> (2018)

2.8.7 Agitation speed

Agitation is a stirring system that is in fermentation. Stirring is done to produce a homogeneous mixture, also increases nutrition, gas, and heat transfer. Efficient mixing with this agitation system is essential for oxygen transfer in aerobic fermentation because microorganisms can take oxygen only from the liquid phase. And changes in dissolved oxygen can be increased through an agitation process. In addition to meeting microbial oxygen requirements, agitation also functions to keep microbes suspended, and the medium solution remains homogeneous. (Scopes, 1994). Table 11 shows the optimum agitation speed for chitinase production of bacteria.

Table 11 Agitation speed for chitinase production by bacteria

Bacterial species	Agitation speed	References
<i>Streptomyces pratensis</i> KLSL55	160 rpm	Shivalee <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. R2	180 rpm	Cheba <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> SV1	250 rpm	Ghorbel-Bellaaj <i>et al.</i> (2012)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. HU1	180 rpm	Dai <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	250 rpm	Kannan <i>et al.</i> (2010)

2.9 Applications of bacterial chitinases

2.9.1 Antifungal agent

The plant pathogenic fungi are the most severe issue globally in the cultivation of economically important crops, particularly in tropical and subtropical areas. (Pohanka, 2016). Chemical fungicides are therefore regularly used to decrease fungal pathogens. But excessive use of these compounds has caused problems related to contamination, natural environmental degradation, and induction pathogen resistance, and has boosted the biomagnification almost three times over the previous 40 years. (Hahn, 2014). These materials may be fatal to insects and bacteria in the ground and may also come into the food chain (Budi *et al.*, 2000). Bacteria are used effectively as biological control of plant pathogens, and chitinase production has been shown to be of significant importance in the elimination of plant diseases (Hong and Hwang, 2006). A quartet of Swiss researchers noted direct proof that some crops protect themselves against pillows by producing an enzyme called chitinase that potently inhibits fungal growth. (Kuddus, 2014). Yan *et al.* (2008) recorded the antifungal activity of chitinases against the four different fungi, and he reported that it was directly correlated to the surface microstructure and the proportion of chitin in the fungal cell wall (analysis by Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)) were used for determination of surface microstructure and percentage of chitin in the cell wall of the four fungi, respectively. Table 12 shows the role of bacterial agents that produced chitinase for the control of fungal plant pathogens.

Table 12 Bacterial agents for biocontrol of fungal plant pathogens

Source	Pathogens	References
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp.	<i>Candida</i> sp.	Subramaniam <i>et al.</i> (2012)
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> S213	<i>Phoma medicaginis</i>	Slimene <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp.	<i>Colletotrichum gleosporoides</i> , <i>Penicillium expansum</i> , <i>Pythium alphanidermatum</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , and <i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	Karthik <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> TV-125	<i>Fusarium culmorum</i>	Senol <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>PaeniBacillus ehimensis</i> KWN38	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> AG-1 (IA), <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f.sp. <i>lycopersici</i> and <i>Phytophthora capsici</i>	Naing <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Bacillus Pumilus</i> MCB-7	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> , <i>Ceratorhiza hydrophila</i> and <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	Rishad <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>PaeniBacillus pasadenensis</i> NCI M 5434	<i>Penicillium</i> sp. and <i>Aspergillus</i> sp	Loni <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i>	Ashwini and Srividya (2014)
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> UM96	<i>Botrytis cinerea</i>	Martínez-Absalón <i>et al.</i> (2014)
<i>Citrobacter freundii</i> haritD11	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> and <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Meruvu and Donthireddy (2014)

Table 12 continued

Source	Pathogens	References
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. P4	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f.sp. <i>lycopersici</i> and <i>Corynesopra cassiicola</i>	Tang-um and Niamsup (2012)
<i>Streptomyces hygroscopicus</i>	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Alternaria alternata</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Sclerotinia sclerotiorum</i> , <i>Phytophthora parasitica</i> , and <i>Botrytis cinerea</i>	Haggag and Abdalh (2012)
<i>Bacillus pumilus</i> SG2	<i>Alternaria brassicicola</i> , <i>Fusarium graminearum</i> and <i>Botrytis cinerea</i>	Dehestani <i>et al.</i> (2010)
<i>Serratia marcescens</i> B4A	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> <i>Bipolaris</i> sp., <i>Alternaria raphanin</i> , <i>A. brassicicola</i>	Zarei <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , and <i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i> .	Karunya (2011)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	<i>Escherichia coli</i> , <i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i> , <i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i> , <i>Lactococcus</i> sp. <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> and <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	Mathur <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. A3	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	Velusamy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Enterobacter</i> sp.KB3	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	Velusamy and Kim (2011)
<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i>	Hua <i>et al.</i> (2010)
<i>Bacillus pumilus</i> SG2	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> , <i>Verticillium</i> sp., <i>Nigrospora</i> sp., <i>Stemphyllium botryosum</i> , and <i>Bipolaris</i> sp.	Ghasemi <i>et al.</i> (2010)

2.9.2 Chitinase as nematocidal agent

Chitinase is another important toxicity factor in the biocontrol of nematodes. Nematicidal chitinases were reported to be produced by various, which killed nematodes via eggshell digestion and cuticle hydrolysis (Yang *et al.*, 2013). As chitin was the main component of the eggshell and cuticle of nematodes and acts as a target for these nematicidal factors (Radwan *et al.*, 2012). Some of the chitinase-producing bacteria that act as nematicides are shown in Table 13.

Table 13 Bacterial chitinase as nematocidal agent

Bacterial species	Nematode	References
<i>PaeniBacillus polymyxa</i> (NFB7), <i>Bacillus megaterium</i> (PSB2) and <i>Bacillus circulans</i> (KSB2)	Root-knot nematode, <i>Meloidogyne incognita</i>	El-Hadad <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> and <i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	Chen <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Lysinibacillus sphaericus</i>	<i>Meloidogyne incognita</i>	Abdel-Salam <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> subsp. <i>subtilis</i> BTN7A, with <i>Escherichia coli</i> as gene transformation	<i>Meloidogyne javanica</i>	Abdel-Salam <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>PaeniBacillus ehimensis</i> RS820	<i>Meloidogyne incognita</i>	Hong <i>et al.</i> (2013)

2.9.3 Chitinase as an insecticidal agent

In agricultural systems, pesticides are used to protect crops from insects and disease. The use of pesticides has also had a significant impact on public health and the environment. The use of biological agents to control crop pests holds excellent promise as an alternative to the use of chemicals. Secondary metabolites and crude microbial chitinase were used to control the population of crop pests (Kramer and Muthukrishnan, 2005). Chitin, a common constituent of the insect's exoskeleton, serves as a scaffold material, supports the epidermis cuticle, and trachea as well as the peritrophic matrix

lining the intestinal epithelium (Merzendorfer and Zimoch, 2003). Some of the chitinase-producing bacteria as insecticidal agents are shown in Table 14.

Table 14 Bacterial chitinase that acts as an insecticidal agent

Bacterial species	Target Insect Species	Expression system	References
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Spodoptera litura</i> Fab	Homologous host	Chandrasekaran <i>et al.</i> (2012)
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> subsp. <i>colmeri</i>	<i>Spodoptera exigua</i> and <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	Heterologous host (<i>Escherichia coli</i>)	Liu <i>et al.</i> (2009)
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> subsp. <i>tenebrionis</i> YBT-9602	<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	Heterologous host (<i>Escherichia coli</i>)	Ni <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>BreviBacillus laterosporus</i> Lak1210	<i>Plutella xylostella</i>	Homologous host	Prasanna <i>et al.</i> (2013)
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i> MP-13	<i>Helopeltis theivora</i>	Homologous host	Suganthi <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>Serratia marcescens</i> SEN	<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	Homologous host	Aggarwal <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Serratia marcescens</i> Xd1	<i>Galleria mellonella</i> and <i>Drosophila melanogaster</i>	Heterologous host (<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>)	Ozgen <i>et al.</i> (2013)
<i>Serratia marcescens</i> WW4	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> and <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	Heterologous host (<i>Escherichia coli</i>)	Danişmazoğlu <i>et al.</i> (2015)
<i>Yersinia entomophaga</i> MH96	<i>Costelytra zealandica</i> , <i>Adoryphorus couloni</i> , <i>Acrossidius tasmaniae</i> , and <i>Plutella</i>	Heterologous host (<i>Escherichia coli</i>)	Busby <i>et al.</i> (2012); Hurst <i>et al.</i> (2011)

2.9.4 Chitinase for isolation of protoplast

Chitinase helps in the formation of protoplasts because it accelerates the degradation of cell walls that contain chitin and thus form protoplasts. This property indirectly contributes to the strain enhancement of different fungi through protoplast fusion and the creation of new economically feasible strains that have been further implemented in various biotechnological sectors. Some bacterial chitinases used for the isolation of protoplast are presented in Table 15.

Table 15 Bacterial chitinase used for isolation of protoplast

Bacterial species	Protoplast-forming activity	References
<i>Oerskovia xanthineolytica</i> NCIM 2839	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Waghmare <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Streptomyces cyaneus</i> SP-27	<i>Schizophyllum commune</i>	Yano <i>et al.</i> (2008)
<i>Streptomyces griseus</i>	<i>Helix pomatia</i>	de Bekker <i>et al.</i> (2009)
<i>Enterobacter</i> sp.	<i>Trichoderma reesei</i> , <i>Pleurotus florida</i> , <i>Agaricus bisporus</i> and <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Dahiya <i>et al.</i> (2005)
<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i> SBK1	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Halder <i>et al.</i> (2014)

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Materials

3.1.1 Chitinous waste

1. Shrimp shell of white shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) was purchased from Chotiawat manufacturing, Songkhla province.
2. Crab Shells of 3-spot swimming crab (*Portunus sanguinolentus*) were purchased from the market in Krabi province.
3. Squid pens of splendid squid (*Loligo formosana*) were purchased from Teppitak Seafood Co., Ltd, Pattani province.

3.1.2 Microorganism

1. 83 *Bacillus* isolates from the culture collection of Microbiology laboratory, Division of Biology, Faculty of Science and Technology, PSU
2. Pathogenic fungi obtained from Thailand Institute of Scientific and Technology Research (TISTR):
 - *Alternaria alternata* TISTR 3435
 - *Aspergillus flavus* TISTR 3041
 - *Aspergillus fumigatus* TISTR 3108
 - *Aspergillus niger* TISTR 3130
 - *Cladosporium cladosporioides* TISTR 3285
 - *Fusarium solani* TISTR 3436
 - *Mucor ruber* TISTR 3006
 - *Penicillium chrysogenum* TISTR 3554
 - *Rhizopus stolonifer* TISTR 3016

3.1.3 Culture media and chemicals

- Shrimp shells powder (Himedia, Mumbai, India)
- Yeast extract (Himedia, Mumbai, India)
- Nutrient agar (NA) (Himedia, Mumbai, India)
- Nutrient broth (NB) (Himedia, Mumbai, India)

- Potato dextrose agar (PDA) (Himedia, Mumbai, India)
- Starch (Univar, Seattle, United States)
- N-acetylglucosamine (NAG) (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany)
- Glucose (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany)
- Lactose (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany)
- Peptone (Himedia, Mumbai, India)
- Maltose (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany)
- NH_4NO_3 (Univar, Seattle, United States)
- 3,5 dinitrosalicylic acid (Sigma, St. Louis, United States)
- NaNO_3 (Univar, Seattle, United States)
- HCl (Univar, Seattle, United States)
- NaOH (Univar, Seattle, United States)
- $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (Univar, Seattle, United States)
- NaCl (Univar, Seattle, United States)
- $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Univar, Seattle, United States)
- KH_2PO_4 (Univar, Seattle, United States)

3.2 Instruments

- Sterilizer (Autoclave Sterilizer 1941X, Hillsville, United States)
- Shaker Incubator (Gallenkamp IOC400.XX2.C, Ebbw Vale, United Kingdom)
- PCR thermal cycler (Perkin Elmer GeneAmp 2400, Sparta Township, United States)
- Forced-Air Incubator (Gallenkamp IPR075.XX1.1, Ebbw Vale, United Kingdom)
- Laminar flow cabinet (ESCO HS 22, Singapore)
- Drying and heating chambers (Binder ED 400, Tuttlingen, Germany)
- UV/VIS Spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific™ Multiskan™ GO, Waltham, United States)
- Refrigerated centrifuge (Eppendorf™ Model 5810 R, Hamburg, Germany)
- Centrifuge (Eppendorf™ Model 5424, Hamburg, Germany)
- pH meter (Fisher Science Education™, 3561712, Waltham, United States).

3.3 Experiment

3.3.1 Preparation of bacteria

83 *Bacillus* isolates were isolated from the marine samples were obtained from the collection of Microbiology laboratory, Biology Division, Science and Technology Faculty, Prince of Songkla University, Pattani Campus, Thailand. The samples were cultured on Nutrient Agar (NA) plates with 3% of NaCl for 24 h and stored in the refrigerator at 4°C.

3.3.2 Preparation of fungi

Plant fungi obtained from TISTR were cultured on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) for five days and stored in the refrigerator at 4°C.

3.3.3 Preparation of colloidal chitin

The colloidal chitin was prepared according to the Souza method (Souza *et al.*, 2009). Ten grams of shrimp chitin powder dissolved into 120 mL concentrated HCl with stirring for one hour. The mixture was filtered through glass wool, and the filtrate was put into 400 mL 50% ethanol with stirring for 20 minutes. The precipitate is filtered into a glass funnel with filter paper and washed with sterile distilled water until colloidal chitin reaches pH 7. The precipitate formed is then autoclaved for 15 minutes at a pressure of 15 psi, reaches a temperature (121 ° C) and stored in a refrigerator at 4°C.

3.3.4 Preparation of chitin substrates

The chitinous biowaste used in this work were the shrimp shell of white shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*), crab shell of 3-spot swimming crab (*Portunus sanguinolentus*), and squid pen of splendid squid (*Loligo formosana*). The dried chitin wastes were ground to obtain small particles by using an electric blender, and then washed with tap water (1:10) and dried in an oven at 55°C for 12 h. The dried chitin waste chips were milled into powder with an electric blender and passed through 120 mesh; thus, their powders were used as the substrate for SmF (Figure 3).

Figure 3 The chitinous waste powder after passed through a 120 mesh (a) shrimp shell powder (b) crab shell powder, and (c) squid pen powder.

3.3.5 Primary screening and selection of chitinase producing bacteria

All the isolates were subjected to the primary screening on chitin agar plates prepared by the method of Chandrasekaran *et al.* (2012) with some modifications. Isolates were cultured on colloidal chitin agar plates (Chandrasekaran *et al.*, 2012) and incubated at 30°C for five days. The chitinolytic bacterial isolates were selected based on the chitinolytic index. The index of chitinolytic activity was determined (Nurdebyandaru *et al.*, 2010), as shown in equation (1).

$$\text{Chitinolytic index} = \frac{\text{Diameter of clear zone (cm)} - \text{diameter of the bacterial colony (cm)}}{\text{The diameter of the bacterial colony (cm)}} \quad (1)$$

The top five chitinolytic bacteria were selected based on the chitinolytic index and tested for antagonistic activity against pathogenic fungi

3.3.6 Screening of antagonistic activity of chitinolytic bacteria against pathogenic fungi

Bacillus isolates tested the ability of its chitinolytic activity against fungi by dual culture techniques (Chaiharn *et al.*, 2013). Briefly, the bacterial isolates were crossed as a single line on the PDA plate and incubated at 28 ° C for 24 hours. A five-day-old fungus was cut using a cork borer with a diameter of five mm. The fungal sample was transferred to a PDA plate which *Bacillus* had grown with a distance of 1 cm from the left and right sides of the bacteria colony and incubated at 30°C. Fungal growth was observed after five days of the incubation period. The percentage of fungal inhibition was calculated using equation (2):

$$\text{Mycelium inhibition (\%)} = \left(\frac{R1 - R2}{R1} \right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where R1 was the growth of the fungus measured from the center of the fungal colony to direction away from the bacterial streaks (mm). R2 was the growth of the fungus measured from the center of the fungal colony towards the bacterial streaks (mm).

3.3.7 Secondary screening of chitinase producing bacteria

Starters of selected *Bacillus* spp. were prepared and cultured on NA for 24 h. A loopful of the bacterial colony was transferred into 100 mL nutrient broth with 3% of NaCl in 250 mL of Erlenmeyer flask in shaking incubator 180 rpm at 30°C for 24 h. The concentration of bacterial cell was prepared by absorbance adjustment of culture broth (OD₆₀₀) value at 0.5. 4 mL of starter were cultured into a 100 mL of colloidal chitin broth in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask and incubated for three days at 30°C in shaking incubator at 180 rpm. Then, the fermentation broth was centrifuged (13,309 g at 4°C for 10 min) to collect the supernatant for chitinase activity assay. The final pH of fermentation broth was measured by pH meter. Microbial growth was determined by filtration of bacterial culture on Whatman ® cellulose filters (No. 1), and the supernatant was analyzed by the photometric technique with the absorbance value at OD₆₀₀ (Thermo Scientific™ Multiskan™ GO spectrophotometer, USA).

3.3.8 Chitinase activity assay

The chitinase activity was assayed by measuring reducing sugar released from colloidal chitin performed by a modified method of Chandrasekaran *et al.* (2012). Briefly, culture supernatant (1 mL) was added to the mixture, which contained 1 mL of 1% colloidal chitin in citrate phosphate buffer (pH 5) and incubated at 37°C for an hour. The reaction mixture was centrifuged (13,309 g at 4°C, 5 min). 1 mL of supernatant was added with 1 mL of 3,5-Dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) reagent and was heated in a water bath at boiling temperature for 5 min. After room temperature, the absorbance was measured at 540 nm. Heat-inactivated enzyme along with the substrate was used as a blank

One chitinase enzyme unit was defined as the number of enzymes that could produce one μmol of reducing sugar (NAG) per hour under reaction conditions. Chitinase activity (U/mL/h) was calculated using the following equation (3).

$$\text{Chitinase unit (U/mL/h)} = A \times 10^3 \times \frac{1}{B} \times C \times \frac{1}{D} \times \frac{1}{E} \times \text{dilution factor} \quad (3)$$

A = N acetyl glucosamine (NAG) standard concentration (mg/mL)

B = Molecular weight of NAG (221.21 g/mole)

C = Total volume of reaction mixture (mL)

D = Reaction time (one hour)

E = Volume of an enzyme (1 mL)

3.3.9 Identification of the selected chitinolytic *Bacillus* sp. strain B26

The selected isolate was characterized by morphological, physiological, and biochemical tests. The results are matched through Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology (Vos *et al.*, 2011). The characterization of the isolate was determined, such as colony shape, elevation, margin, the color of the colony, spore formation, citrate utilization, urease production, catalase test, starch hydrolysis, Voges–Proskauer reaction, growth at different pH, temperature, and NaCl (Appendix A and B). Furthermore, the molecular identification of 16S DNA sequence was analyzed.

Genomic DNA isolation was performed using Phenol-chloroform extraction (attachment). The isolated DNA was checked for its quality and concentration by agarose gel electrophoresis on a UV transilluminator. The 16S rRNA region was amplified with universal forward and reverse bacterial primers. The PCR amplification was performed using a PCR thermal cycler (Perkin Elmer GeneAmp 2400) using PCR specific primer (o27F and o1492R). Total PCR reaction of 200 μL contains 0.5 μL of genomic DNA, 100 μL Taq 2x Master Mix (New England Biolabs), 2 μL each primer with 10 μM primers and 96 μL of distilled water. Primary heating step for 2 min at 95°C, followed by 25 cycles of denaturation for 1 min at 95°C, annealing for 60 s at 53°C, and extension for 90 s at 72°C followed by a final extension step for 5 min at 72°C. The PCR-amplified product was analyzed on 1% agarose gel containing ethidium bromide (0.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) with GeneRuler™ 1 kb DNA Ladder marker (Fermentas). PCR products of about 1500 bp were purified and sequenced at Bioneer sequencing

company, Republic of Korea. The sequencing results were analyzed by using the BioEdit sequence alignment editor then aligned with the 16S rRNA database using the BLAST-N program.

3.3.10 Optimization of chitinase production

Studies on medium optimization for chitinase production using variable methods reduce the time and expense because they can detect the real optimum level of factors in less time. Besides, the culture medium components have a significant influence on the microbial production of extracellular chitinases.

3.3.10.1 Effect of different substrates and concentrations on chitinase production

The Effect of different substrates (1%) on chitinase production by the selected bacterial strain was investigated. Substrates including shrimp shell powder (SSP), crab shell powder (CSP), and squid pen powder (SPP) were added in the basic medium containing (g/L) yeast extract 0.5; $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ 1.0; $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.3; KH_2PO_4 1.36; NaCl 30 pH 7.0. 4 mL (0.5 OD_{600}) of *Bacillus* sp. B26 inoculum was cultured into 100 mL of medium in a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask and incubated at 30°C for three days under shaking condition at 180 rpm. The final pH of fermentation broth was measured using a pH meter. Measurement of microbial growth was conducted by filtering culture medium on Whatman ® cellulose filters grade 1 to eliminate colloidal chitin, and the optical density was analyzed at 600 nm. Different concentrations of selected substrates (0.5, 1, 2, and 3%) were applied, and chitinase assay was performed as per standard protocol.

3.3.10.2 Effect of additional carbon source and concentration on chitinase production

The effects of various carbon sources (1%), namely glucose, lactose, maltose, and N-acetylglucosamine (NAG), were used as additional supplements in optimized media for maximum enzyme production. Media without additional carbon sources was used as a control. 4 mL (0.5 OD_{600}) of *Bacillus* sp. B26 inoculum was cultured into 100 mL of medium in a 250 mL of Erlenmeyer flask and incubated at 30°C for three days under shaking condition at 180 rpm. The final pH of fermentation

broth was measured using a pH meter. Measurement of microbial growth was conducted by filtering culture medium on Whatman® cellulose filters grade 1 to eliminate colloidal chitin, and the optical density was analyzed at 600 nm. Chitinase assay was performed as per standard protocol. Different concentrations of selected additional carbon source (0, 0.5, 1, and 2%) were applied in optimized media and conditions to determine the best additional carbon source concentration.

3.3.10.3 Effect of nitrogen sources and concentrations on chitinase production

The effect of nitrogen sources (1%) viz. sodium nitrate (NaNO_3), ammonium nitrate (NH_3NO_4), peptone, and yeast extract were used as additional nitrogen sources in optimized media for maximum chitinase production. Media without additional nitrogen sources was used as a control. 4 mL (0.5 OD_{600}) of *Bacillus* sp. B26 inoculum was cultured into 100 mL of medium in a 250 mL of Erlenmeyer flask and incubated at 30°C for three days under shaking condition at 180 rpm. The final pH of fermentation broth was measured using a pH meter. Measurement of microbial growth was conducted by filtering culture medium on Whatman® cellulose filters grade 1 to eliminate colloidal chitin, and the optical density was analyzed at 600 nm. Chitinase assay was performed as per standard protocol. Different concentrations of nitrogen source (0, 0.5, 1, and 2%) were applied in optimized media to determine the best nitrogen source concentration.

3.3.10.4 Effect the NaCl concentrations on chitinase production

NaCl concentrations (0, 1, 2, 3, and 4%) were used to test the effect of chitinase production. 4 mL (0.5 OD_{600}) of *Bacillus* sp. B26 inoculum was cultured into 100 mL of medium in a 250 mL of Erlenmeyer flask and incubated at 30°C for three days under shaking condition at 180 rpm. The final pH of fermentation broth was measured using a pH meter. Measurement of microbial growth was conducted by filtering culture medium on Whatman® cellulose filters grade 1 to eliminate colloidal chitin, and the optical density was analyzed at 600 nm. Chitinase assay was performed as per standard protocol.

3.3.10.5 Effect of initial pH of a medium on chitinase production

The chitinase production was optimized with different initial pH of the previously optimized medium adjusted to 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9. 4 mL (0.5 OD₆₀₀) of *Bacillus* sp. B26 inoculum was cultured into 100 mL of medium in a 250 mL of Erlenmeyer flask and incubated at 30°C for three days under shaking condition at 180 rpm. The final pH of fermentation broth was measured using a pH meter. Measurement of microbial growth was conducted by filtering culture medium on Whatman® cellulose filters grade 1 to eliminate colloidal chitin, and the optical density was analyzed at 600 nm. Chitinase assay was performed as per standard protocol.

3.3.10.6 Effect of incubation time on chitinase production

For optimum incubation time, the *Bacillus* culture was cultured for seven days in the previously optimized medium. 4 mL (0.5 OD₆₀₀) of *Bacillus* sp. B26 inoculum was cultured into 100 mL of medium in a 250 mL of Erlenmeyer flask and incubated at 30°C for seven days under shaking condition at 180 rpm. The final pH of fermentation broth was measured using a pH meter. Measurement of microbial growth was conducted by filtering culture medium on Whatman® cellulose filters grade 1 to eliminate colloidal chitin, and the optical density was analyzed at 600 nm. Chitinase assay was performed as per standard protocol. Bacteria growth and chitinase production were checked every day for seven days.

3.3.11 Evaluation of the antifungal activity of crude chitinase

For the preparation of crude chitinase from *Bacillus* sp. B26, an optimized medium containing 2% of squid pen powder, 0.5% of sodium nitrate, 2% of NaCl in the basal medium (0.05% of yeast extract, 0.1% of (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.03% of MgSO₄•7H₂O and 0.136% of KH₂PO₄) with initial medium pH 7 was used. 4 mL of starter inoculum (0.5 OD₆₀₀) was cultured in a 100 mL of optimized medium broth in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask and incubated for three days at 30°C under shaking condition at 180 rpm. The fermentation broth was centrifuged with 13,309 g at 4°C for 10 min to collect the cell-free culture supernatant. The obtained culture supernatant obtained was used as a source of crude chitinase. Antifungal activity of crude chitinase was tested against pathogenic fungi by well diffusion assay (Frag *et al.*, 2016).

Several fungi including *Alternaria alternata* TISTR 3435, *Aspergillus flavus* TISTR 3041, *Aspergillus fumigatus* TISTR 3108, *Aspergillus niger* TISTR 3130,

Cladosporium cladosporioides TISTR 3285, *Fusarium solani* TISTR 3436, *Mucor ruber* TISTR 3006, *Penicillium chrysogenum* TISTR 3554, and *Rhizopus stolonifer* TISTR 3016 were used for antifungal activity testing of chitinase.

The preparation of fungi was carried out by growing fungi on the PDA plate for five days. 5 mm diameter fungal plug was cut with a cork borer and transferred to the center of the PDA plate. Then, four wells were made using the aseptic cork borer around with equal distance from the center of the plates. Equal aliquots (150 μ L) of crude chitinase (sample), uninoculated crude (negative control), 5-min-boiled crude chitinase, and 2 μ g/mL amphotericin B (positive control) were presented onto wells. The plates were incubated at 30°C for five days. The percentage of mycelial growth inhibition of the test fungi was calculated using the following equation (4) (Chang *et al.*, 2003).

$$\text{Mycelium growth inhibition (\%)} = \left(\frac{R1 - R2}{R1} \right) \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Where R1 was the fungal growth radius distance (mm) measured from the center of the fungal colony towards the negative control well and R2 was the fungal growth radius distance (mm) towards the sample well. Generally, if the percentage of inhibition was higher than 20%, the tested fungi were considered inhibited.

3.4 Data analysis

All the optimization studies were carried out in triplicate with a one-factor-at-a-time method (OFAT). The data were analyzed using a single-factor analysis of variance (ANOVA). All the data were shown as the mean with standard deviation.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Primary screening and selection of chitinase producing bacteria

The 83 *Bacillus* isolates were isolated from marine samples and stored as the collection of Microbiology Laboratory, Biology Division, Faculty of Science and Technology, PSU Pattani. The chitinolytic activity of chitinase of isolates was qualitatively determined in the term of the chitinolytic index. The chitinolytic activity test was initiated by the cultivation of the isolates on medium agar containing 1% colloidal chitin with an incubation time of five days at room temperature. The chitinolytic index was obtained based on the clear of inhibition diameter with colony diameter on colloidal chitin agar. Chitinolytic index values become parameters that indicate the presence of extracellular chitinase activity secreted by isolates. The chitinase producing bacterial isolates was characterized by clear of inhibition around the growing bacterial colonies, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Plate assay showing the chitinase activity of the *Bacillus* sp. B26 on colloidal chitin agar after five days at 30°C.

The chitinolytic index is generally used as one of the screening methods. This method is widely used because it is capable of screening large amounts of chitinolytic isolates in a short time. Chitin substrate in the culture medium can induce a group of chitinolytic enzymes, such as exochitinase and endochitinase (Chernin *et al.*, 1995) and one most used in the form of colloidal chitin (Murthy and Bleakley, 2012).

From the results of testing about the chitinolytic index, 17% of tested bacterial isolates were chitinolytic bacteria (Figure 5). There were 14 from 83 of isolates with clear of inhibition occurrence by chitinolytic activity, as shown in Table 16.

Figure 5 Distribution of chitinolytic *Bacillus* spp. from marine samples

Table 16 Chitinolytic activity of *Bacillus* isolates

Isolates	Diameter of colony (cm)	Clear zone (cm)	Chitinolytic index
B26	0.95±0.01	1.55±0.01	0.63±0.00
B07	0.97±0.01	1.54±0.01	0.59±0.01
B19	1.04±0.01	1.65±0.01	0.58±0.01
B10	1.06±0.02	1.56±0.05	0.48±0.02
B20	1.22±0.03	1.74±0.01	0.43±0.02
B18	1.12±0.02	1.56±0.02	0.40±0.01
B02	1.05±0.01	1.45±0.00	0.38±0.01
B01	1.12±0.02	1.52±0.02	0.36±0.01
B09	1.45±0.02	1.85±0.02	0.28±0.00
B12	1.14±0.02	1.44±0.01	0.26±0.01
B04	1.05±0.01	1.30±0.02	0.24±0.02
B13	1.12±0.02	1.32±0.02	0.18±0.00
B16	1.42±0.01	1.59±0.01	0.12±0.01
B40	1.71±0.01	1.81±0.01	0.06±0.00

Based on primary screening, *Bacillus* sp. B26 showed the highest chitinolytic index 0.63, as shown in Table 16. In comparison, Hiraga *et al.* (1997) found that 4% of marine bacterial isolates showed clear inhibition in the medium chitin. Chandrasekaran *et al.* (2012) found 74.07% of bacterial samples isolated from soil samples capable of producing clear of inhibition in the colloidal chitin agar medium.

According to the report of Bai *et al.* (2016), a total of 74 from 256 bacterial genomes from the soil environment meet the criteria to be considered a genome of bacteria containing chitinase. For aquatic habitats, a total of 36 out of 401 bacterial genomes met the requirements to be considered as bacterial genomes containing chitinase. The proportion of bacterial genomes comprising chitinase genes for terrestrial bacteria (29 percent) was therefore much higher than for aquatic bacteria (9 percent). The genome variety of chitinase produces bacteria less in aquatic habitats due to many sources of dissolved organic and organic material (Ogawa and Tanoue, 2003). Differences between aquatic and soils bacteria containing chitinase in relative abundance can show that chitinase genes can generally be found more in bacteria living in terrestrial environments than aquatic (Bai *et al.* 2016).

The modular structure of chitinase in bacterial genomes shows distinctions between aquatic and terrestrial bacteria that may be linked to the distinct chitinous resources they use. The primary source of chitin in aquatic and terrestrial habitats is exoskeletal arthropods and fungal cell walls. Their composition is very distinct, given that arthropod exoskeletons and fungal cell walls are considered multi-phase composites. α -chitin fibers are integrated into a protein matrix with the capacity of minerals such as calcite for the arthropod exoskeletons. (Raabe *et al.*, 2006). Fungal cell walls have a distinct structure. The last one consists primarily of α -chitin, glucans, mannans, and glycoproteins, which are interlinked with chitin, glucans, and glycoproteins (Bowman and Free, 2006). Moreover, chitin fibers differ in their ultrastructure between arthropods and fungi (Raabe *et al.*, 2006). Such differences between arthropod exoskeletons and fungal cell walls should be expected to be reflected in adaptations of bacterial degrading chitin. Based on the chitinolytic index, the top five chitinolytic *Bacillus* isolates selected for antagonistic activity against pathogenic fungi.

4.2 Screening of antagonistic activity of chitinolytic bacteria against pathogenic fungi

The top five selected isolates based on the chitinolytic index from the primary screening were tested for their antagonistic activity toward pathogenic fungi. The inhibitory test was carried out by the dual culture method for the growth of fungi and bacteria simultaneously on PDA media and incubated for five days at 30°C. In the present study, 5 of *Bacillus* isolates, which comprised around 29% of the inhibitory of fungi. The results of the antagonistic test showed that *Bacillus* sp. B26 was able to inhibit at least 4 of the nine plant pathogenic fungi (Table 17), which were characterized by using inhibitory zones. The percentage of fungal inhibition of *Bacillus* sp. B26 against *Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium solani*, *Mucor ruber*, and *Penicillium chrysogenum* was 74.51, 69.49, 30.95, and 46.51, respectively.

Table 17 Antagonistic activity of chitinolytic *Bacillus* isolates against various pathogenic fungi.

Pathogenic fungi	Percentage of fungal inhibition by <i>Bacillus</i> isolates (Mean±SD)				
	B07	B10	B19	B20	B26
<i>Alternaria alternata</i> TISTR 3435	0	68.5±3.64	0	0	74.5±3.4
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> TISTR 3041	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> TISTR 3108	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Aspergillus niger</i> TISTR 3130	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i> TISTR 3285	0	0	0	0	0

Table 17 continued

Pathogenic fungi	Percentage of inhibition (Mean \pm SD)				
	B07	B10	B19	B20	B26
<i>Cladosporium</i>					
<i>cladosporioides</i> TISTR 3285	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Fusarium solani</i>					
TISTR 3436	56.25 \pm 0	65.2 \pm 4.67	63.97 \pm 1.27	63.24 \pm 1.27	69.49 \pm 5.19
<i>Mucor ruber</i>					
TISTR 3006	0	0	0	0	30.95 \pm 4.12
<i>Penicillium</i>					
<i>chrysogenum</i> TISTR 3554	38.46 \pm 0	42.86 \pm 0	41.75 \pm 5.56	41.9 \pm 1.65	46.51 \pm 3.57
<i>Rhizopus</i>					
<i>stolonifer</i> TISTR 3016	0	0	0	00	0

The mechanisms of action of bacterial antagonists, including *Bacillus* spp., play an essential role in determining the most effective application that maximally inhibits the growth of plant pathogenic fungi and function on a harvested host plant (Droby *et al.*, 1992). *Bacillus* spp. suppresses postharvest pathogens, multiple mechanisms have been suggested including (1) production of various antifungal metabolites, lipopeptides, or antibiotics (Ramachandran *et al.*, 2014); (2) synthesis of hydrolytic enzymes which can destroy pathogenic fungal cells and a number of pathogenic effector compounds (Wang *et al.*, 2013b).

Possible mechanisms of antagonistic function of *Bacillus* bacteria can be attributed to the synthesis of extracellular hydrolases such as chitinases and β 1,3-glucanases capable of destroying the structural polysaccharides of the fungal cell wall (chitin and glucans) and lysing the hyphae of fungi (Yáñez-Mendizábal *et al.*, 2011). Research on *Bacillus* spp. showed the most contribution to lysis of the native mycelium of various species of phytopathogenic fungi *Fusarium solani* (Hammami *et al.*, 2013), *Penicillium chrysogenum* (Karunya, 2011), and *Alternaria alternata* (Aktuganov *et al.*,

2007). Chitinolytic activity is often considered to be one of the most important criteria determining the antagonistic properties of bacteria. However, the question of the antagonistic function of many bacterial chitinases must be proven by testing antifungal activity through chitinase produced.

4.3 Secondary screening of chitinase producing bacteria

Five selected *Bacillus* isolates were tested to ensure their potential of chitinase in colloidal chitin medium broth as secondary screening. The influence of incubation time on the chitinase production and bacterial growth are shown in Table 18.

The maximum activity of chitinase (0.75 U/mL/h) was produced by the *Bacillus* sp. B26 during the growth of the logarithmic phase after 72 h incubation with the OD₆₀₀ value at 0.46. However, there were no significant differences in enzyme activity among the bacteria found in this test. The crude chitinases obtained from chitinolytic bacteria were carried out for testing antifungal activity.

Table 18 Chitinase activity and growth of the selected *Bacillus* sp. B26 after incubation for 72 hours

Chitinolytic bacteria	Chitinase activity (U/mL/h)	Bacterial growth (OD ₆₀₀)
B07	0.74±0.06	0.39±0.02
B10	0.72±0.01	0.44±0.01
B19	0.74±0.03	0.46±0.03
B20	0.75±0.08	0.43±0.03
B26	0.75±0.01	0.46±0.01

The results showed that only crude chitinase of the *Bacillus* sp. B26 was the potent antifungal activity than the other four isolates. The *Bacillus* sp. B26 was able to inhibit at least 2 of the nine types of fungi that were *Fusarium solani* and *Penicillium chrysogenum* about 44.5% and 34.76%, as shown in Table 19. Research on four different *Bacillus* spp. had inhibitory activity against *Fusarium* growth by 60–70% in comparison to the controls. *Fusarium* cell walls are composed of chitin, α -1,3-glucans, and β -1,3-glucans (Schoffemeer *et al.*, 1999), suggesting that chitin-degrading enzymes and glucanases are likely to be responsible for *Bacillus* sp. B26 effects on fungal hyphal.

Table 19 Antifungal activity of crude chitinase of *Bacillus* sp. B26 against various pathogenic fungi

Pathogenic fungi	Percentage of fungal inhibitory by <i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26 (Mean±SD)				
	B07	B10	B19	B20	B26
<i>Alternaria alternata</i> TISTR 3435	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> TISTR 3041	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> TISTR 3108	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Aspergillus niger</i> TISTR 3130	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i> TISTR 3285	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Fusarium solani</i> TISTR 3436	0	0	0	0	44.52±2.01
<i>Mucor ruber</i> TISTR 3006	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i> TISTR 3554	0	0	0	0	34.76±5.77
<i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i> TISTR 3016	0	0	0	0	0

The chitin has an intrinsic variability due to its natural origin, and it exists in several forms with their specific properties (Aranaz *et al.*, 2009). This polymer of fungi possesses principally the same structure as the chitin occurring in other organisms. The difference in chitinolytic ability must result from the subsite structure in the binding cleft (Sasaki *et al.*, 2002). This implies that why the enzyme did not show significant antifungal activity against other fungi. Then *Bacillus* sp. B26 was selected for bacterial identification.

4.4 Identification of *Bacillus* sp. B26

The morphological, physiological, and biochemical characters of *Bacillus* sp. B26 was identified according to the Bergey Manual method. The identification of *Bacillus* sp. B26 was done primarily by studying the colony morphology, followed by gram staining. After screening and observing the colony morphology, the bacterial strain was subjected to various biochemical tests like citrate utilization, urease production, oxidase test, catalase test, starch hydrolysis, Voges-Proskauer reaction, and casein hydrolysis. *Bacillus* sp. B26 was gram-positive, and spore-forming bacterial rod. The results of the biochemical tests for *Bacillus* sp. B26 is summarized in Table 20. *Bacillus* sp. B26 showed positive results for the urease production, catalase test, starch

hydrolysis, and casein hydrolysis then showed negative results for the citrate utilization, oxidase test, and Voges-Proskauer reaction. The utilization of different sugar sources was tested using basal carbon medium supplemented with different sugars. *Bacillus* sp. B26 produced acid and gas from carbohydrates such as arabinose, lactose, maltose, glucose, sucrose, galactose, mannitol, and fructose. Based on the results of identification by Bergey manual method, characteristics of *Bacillus* sp. B26 related to *Bacillus cereus*.

Table 20 Characterization of *Bacillus* sp. B26

Colony properties	<i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26
Morphology test	
Colony shape and size	Circular, 2-3 mm
Margin	Entire
Elevation	Raised
Surface	Smooth
Color	Creamish
Gram's reaction	+ve
Cellular morphology	Bacilli
Spore (s)	+ve
Physiological tests	
Growth at the temperature (°C)	
18	+
22	++
37	+++
50	++
60	-

Table 20 continued

Colony properties	<i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26
Growth at pH	
5	+
6	++
7	+++
8	+++
9	++
10	+
11	-
12	-
Growth in NaCl (%)	
0	+
1	++
2	+++
3	++
4	++
5	+
7.0	-
10.0	-
Biochemical tests	
Voges-Proskauer test	Negative
Oxidase test	Negative
Citrate test	Negative
Catalase test	Positive
Casein hydrolysis	Positive
Starch hydrolysis	Positive
Urease production	Positive
Utilization of carbohydrates	
Fructose	Positive
Mannitol	Positive

Table 20 continued

Colony properties	<i>Bacillus</i> sp. B26
Utilization of carbohydrates (acid production)	
Galactose	Positive
Sucrose	Positive
Glucose	Positive
Maltose	Positive
Lactose	Positive
Arabinose	Positive

+++ = highest growth (>1 OD₆₀₀), ++ = good growth (0.5 - 1 OD₆₀₀), + = average growth (0 - 0.5 OD₆₀₀), - = no growth

4.5 Analysis of DNA sequences

Bacillus sp. B26 was subsequently identified molecularly based on the 16S rRNA sequence. The results of the measurement of concentration and purity of genomic DNA showed that bacterial genomic DNA concentrations obtained were 56.5 ng/μL. Genomic DNA was made into a template in the 16S rRNA coding gene PCR process rRNA. The results of the visualization of the amplification of the 16S rRNA encoding gene on 1% agarose gel produced are 1.5 kb DNA products (Figure 6).

Figure 6 PCR amplification of *Bacillus* sp. B26

In GenBank, the homology of the isolate partial 16S rRNA gene sequence was analyzed using the BLAST algorithm. For phylotype identification, only the highest-scored BLAST result was considered. *Bacillus* sp. B26 linear DNA (1.5 kb) gave maximum homology (99%) with *Bacillus paramycooides*, a member group of *Bacillus cereus* (Liu *et al.*, 2017).

4.6 Optimization of chitinase production

4.6.1 Effect of different substrates on chitinase activity and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26

The efficiency of *Bacillus* sp. B26 to degrade chitin in the synthetic medium led to design an experiment for studying their efficiency to produce chitinase by waste containing chitin. The effect of various chitinous substrates (1% w/v) on chitinase production was tested. This study showed markedly chitinase activity in varied over a wide range (0.93-2.3 U/mL/h). The obtained results are presented in Figure 7 that showed a response of *Bacillus* sp. B26 to use waste containing chitin as an energy source for the production of chitinase. The obtained results revealed that all the tested waste containing chitin was able to induce the production of chitinase of *Bacillus* sp. B26. Among the four tested chitinous wastes, the squid pen powder gave the maximum chitinase production (2.3 U/mL/h) when the culture reached a cell density of 2.0 (OD₆₀₀), and the final pH of the medium was 8.06. Through the one-factor-at-a-time (OFAT) optimization method, a 3.07-fold increase of chitinase production was

achieved from a medium containing squid pen powder when compared to the primary colloidal chitin medium. The maximum chitinase production was found in the medium containing squid pen powder and followed by shrimp shell powder, crab shell powder, and colloidal chitin, respectively. The same finding was found in *Streptomyces thermocarboxydus* (Tran *et al.*, 2019).

The superior effect of squid pen powder on chitinase production could be attributed to many reasons. The β -chitin type was found as a significant component in the squid pen, as stated by Howard *et al.* (2003). The β -chitin, as mentioned before by Shigemasa *et al.* (1994) and Svitil *et al.* (1997) characterized by an open parallel unpacked structure than the closed antiparallel packed structure of α -chitin found in most of the arthropods including crabs and shrimps. Then, β -chitin from squid pen exhibits higher accessibility to water, and thus to water-soluble reagents indicate it has low mineralization, especially by the absence of calcium carbonate. In contrast, shrimp and crab shell constituting the cuticles of arthropods (Chaussard and Domard, 2004).

Some studies reported that squid pen powder was used as a substrate for chitinase production by *Chondrus verrucosus* (Shirota *et al.*, 2008), *Serratia ureilytica* (Wang *et al.*, 2009) and *Bacillus subtilis* (Liang *et al.*, 2014). According to Cuong *et al.* (2016), squid pen from *Loligo chensis*, *Illex argentines*, and *Ommastrephes bartramii* have chitin composition of 34, 31, 35-40 (%), respectively which are higher than crab including *Callinectes sapidus*, *Chionoectes opilio* and shrimp; *Pandalus borealis*, *Crangon crangon*, *Penaeus monodon* with chitin composition at 13.5, 26.6, 17.0, 17.8, and 40.4%, respectively (Synowiecki and Al-Khateeb, 2000). Low chitinase production was found in the colloidal chitin medium broth. These results were agreed with a previous report (De-Hui *et al.*, 2011) that colloidal chitin produced chitinase lower than chitin medium from thermophilic *PaeniBacillus* sp. Hui. Colloidal chitin is complicated to be processed, direct application of chitin as the carbon source is preferable in industrial production.

Figure 7 Effect of the substrate on chitinase production and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

4.6.2 Effect of substrate concentration on chitinase activity and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26

Four different squid pen powder concentrations ranging from 0.5, 1, 2, and 3% were examined for chitinase production and bacterial growth shown in Figure 8. The maximum chitinase activity was produced by using 2% of squid pen powder (3.38 U/mL/h) when the culture reached a cell density of 2.02 at OD₆₀₀, and the final pH of the medium was 8.39. The chitinase activity decreased by using 3%, 1%, and 0.5% of the SPP medium. The effect of 0.5% and 1% of squid pen powder concentration on chitinase activity were significantly lower than of SPP 2% ($p < 0.05$). The enzyme activity increased by 2.39-fold when increasing the squid pen powder concentration in medium from 0.5% to 2%. A similar observation has also been reported by *Serratia marcescens* DSM 30121T with maximum chitinase activity (0.37 U/mL/min) in medium culture containing 2% of chitin (Lamine *et al.*, 2012). A decrease in chitinase activity produced by *Bacillus* sp. B26 was found at 3% of carbon source concentration that was similar to *Serratia marcescens* DSM 30121T. This might be due to a

hampering reaction of carbon source serving as the substrate, or accumulation of metabolites produced from chitin decomposition, which showed themselves as synthesis inhibitors. Besides, the increase in carbon source concentration in the medium was found to increase the medium viscosity, thus reduced the dissolved oxygen, which causes the lower values of bacterial growth and enzyme activity (Jeremy *et al.*, 1997).

Figure 8 Effect of squid pen powder concentration on chitinase production and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

4.6.3 Effect of additional carbon sources on chitinase production and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26

The effect of additional carbon sources in squid pen powder (SPP) medium on chitinase production by *Bacillus* sp. B26 was studied. A total of four different carbon sources (1%) such as glucose, lactose, N-acetylglucosamine (NAG), and maltose were tested. The medium without additional carbon source was used as control. *Bacillus* sp. B26 produced maximum chitinase activity in squid pen powder medium without an additional carbon source, as shown in Figure 9. The SPP medium without additional carbon source gave maximum chitinase activity of 3.65 U/mL/h. The optical density

(OD₆₀₀) of bacterial culture of *Bacillus* sp. B26 was 1.79, and the final pH of broth was 7.71. The maximum chitinase production followed by lactose, glucose, NAG, and maltose, respectively. In the present study, NAG and maltose inhibited significantly of chitinase production ($p < 0.05$). The results were agreed with previous reports (Chaiham *et al.*, 2013 and Aida *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 9 Effect of additional carbon source on chitinase production and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

The expression of chitinase from *Bacillus* sp. B26 by chitin as a sole carbon source, while it was repressed in the presence of sugar compound. The preference of bacteria chitinase was controlled by the Carbon Catabolite Repression (CCR) mechanism (Vinuselvi *et al.*, 2012), These findings suggested that other polymer hydrolyzing enzymes, such as amylases and β -glucanases, were synthesized, which in turn produced glucose at concentrations high enough to cause catabolite repression (Frändberg and Schnürer, 1994).

However, the addition of different carbon sources in the culture medium was reported to increase chitinase production by some microorganisms, including glucose and NAG by *Bacillus* sp. R2 (Cheba *et al.*, 2017), fructose by *Streptomyces pratensis* KLSL55 (Shivalee *et al.*, 2018), and starch by *Aeromonas hydrophila* (Saima *et al.*, 2013). Chitinase production was induced by chitin and inhibited in the presence of monosaccharides. These compounds inhibited enzyme biosynthesis and presented with low chitinase activity when they were used as carbon sources. Lactose, sucrose, and maltose were found to decrease chitinase production by *Cohnella* sp. A01 (approximately 70–80%) (Aliabadi *et al.*, 2016), but some reports showed that lactose increased chitinase production by *Bacillus licheniformis* (Gomaa, 2012) and sucrose showed an increase in chitinase production by *Streptomyces* sp. (Sowmya *et al.*, 2012). Nevertheless, chitin gave the highest enzyme activity (100%) (Aliabadi *et al.*, 2016).

4.6.4 Effect of nitrogen source on chitinase production and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26

The effect of nitrogen sources on chitinase production and bacterial growth was studied by using 1% of various organic nitrogen (peptone and yeast extract) and inorganic nitrogen (NaNO_3 and NH_4NO_3). As the results are shown in Figure 10, inorganic nitrogen sources were the favorable nitrogen sources for the chitinase production by *Bacillus* sp. B26. NaNO_3 showed excellent results for maximum chitinase production (4.67 U/mL/h) when the optical density (OD_{600}) of bacterial culture was 1.73, and the final pH of the culture broth was 7.88. In the case of organic nitrogen sources, peptone and yeast extract had severe effects.

It may be due to sodium nitrate is the inorganic nitrogen form of more straightforward assimilation and also because of lower energetic costs of metabolization. Results from the study supported by previous reports that favorable inorganic nitrogen sources for chitinase production from microbial sources such as ammonium sulfate and sodium nitrate by *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Chaiharn *et al.*, 2013) and ammonium nitrate by *Cohnella* sp. A01 (Aliabadi *et al.*, 2016).

Results from this study were supported by previous reports that the influence of organic nitrogen sources was unable to accelerate the chitinolytic activity when compared with an inorganic nitrogen source (Meena *et al.*, 2014b). This study showed

that yeast extract and peptone inhibited the chitinase production due to too much concentration of organic nitrogen in the broth for this fermentation. However, there was some report about yeast extract and peptone to enhance chitinase production by *Acinetobacter parvus* compared to inorganic nitrogen sources (Kim *et al.*, 2017). The importance of nitrogen source on chitinolytic activity by different species of *Bacillus* had been reported by Tasharrofi *et al.* (2011), Gomaa (2012), and Cheba *et al.* (2018).

Figure 10 Effect of nitrogen sources on chitinase production and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

4.6.5 Effect of nitrogen source concentrations on chitinase activity and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26

To investigate the optimal nitrogen source concentration on chitinase production and bacterial growth, the NaNO₃ was added to the culture medium at 0.5, 1, 2, and 3% (w/v). The maximum chitinase production (4.71 U/mL/h) was found in 0.5% of sodium nitrate, as shown in Figure 11. The cell density reached 1.8 OD₆₀₀, and the final pH of the broth was 7.98. The concentration of NaNO₃ that gave the maximum chitinase production was found at 0.5%, followed by 1%, 2%, and 3%, respectively.

Effects of 2%, and 3% of NaNO_3 concentration on chitinase production were significantly lower than concentration at 0.5% ($p < 0.05$). Concentrations of NaNO_3 higher than 0.5% exhibited in chitinase activity. Data of this study was agreed with those reports of many researchers. The 0.5% of organic nitrogen source was the optimum concentration for chitinase production from *Bacillus circulans* (Watanabe *et al.*, 1990), *Streptomyces cinereoruber* (Okazaki and Tagawa, 1991), *Enterobacter* sp. (Dahiya *et al.*, 2005), *Cellulomonas flavigena* (Chen *et al.*, 1997), *Salinivibrio costicola* (Aunpad and Panbangrad, 2003), and inorganic nitrogen from *Streptomyces pratensis* KLSL55 (Shivalee *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 11 Effect of sodium nitrate concentration on chitinase production and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

4.6.6 Effect of NaCl concentrations on chitinase production

The five different NaCl concentrations from 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4% (w/v) were examined for chitinase production and bacterial growth as shown in Figure 12. The

maximum chitinase production was found at 2% of NaCl (6.34 U/mL/h). The NaCl was a necessary factor for enzyme production because enzyme production observed at levels significantly increase 3.8-fold from 0 to 2% of NaCl. Comparable results were obtained by Cheba *et al.* (2018) and Aunpad and Panbangrad (2003), the NaCl concentration (2.5%), and (3%) were optimized for chitinase production by marine *Bacillus* sp. R2 and *Salinivibrio costicola*, respectively.

The chitinase activation by Na⁺ was reported by many authors (Yuli *et al.*, 2004; Aunpad and Panbangrad, 2003; Tsujibo *et al.*, 1993; and Cheba *et al.*, 2018). Metal ions may stimulate the enzyme activity by acting as a binding link enzyme and substrate, combining with both, and thus holding the substrate at the active site of the enzyme (Cheba *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 12 Effect of NaCl concentration on chitinase production and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

The results showed that the *Bacillus* sp. B26 grew well in medium containing 2% of NaCl with culture reached 2.02 OD₆₀₀. This condition showed in hyperosmotic

media containing concentrations of Na^+ that had a strict chloride dependence for growth or were significantly stimulated by chloride in *Bacillus* sp. B26. According to Galinski and Trüper (1994), for thriving under conditions of elevated osmolarity, it is essential for the cells to measure external osmolarity and to adjust their metabolism accordingly, e.g., by inducing the biosynthesis or uptake of osmolytes. According to Lanyi (1979), a different function of Cl^- might be in Na^+ homeostasis. Na^+ is cytotoxic, and all living cells tend to expel high sodium ions from their cytoplasm.

4.6.7 Effect of initial pH of the medium on chitinase production

The initial pH value of the medium has a significant effect on cell growth, cell membrane permeability, enzyme biosynthesis, secretion, activity, and stability (Takao *et al.*, 1985). Although the exact relationship of pH to metabolite production is still not clear, some elementary tests have been carried out to find the pH capable of supporting high enzyme synthesis. The effects of various initial pH values (5, 6, 7, 8, and 9) investigation, as shown in Figure 13. Chitinase activity was bell-shaped with maximum chitinase production found at pH 7.0 (6.3 U/mL/h) with a final pH of broth reached 7.8. A high chitinase production was observed at pH 7, followed by pH 8, 6, 5, and 9, respectively. The same results were found in *Bacillus cereus*, *Streptomyces rubiginosus*, *PaeniBacillus* sp. D3, and *Aeromonas punctate* (Liang *et al.*, 2014; Jha *et al.*, 2016; Chrisnasari *et al.*, 2016; and Saima *et al.*, 2013).

Increasing or decreasing the pH value than 7.0 caused decreasing in chitinase activity. Similar results were reported by Kao *et al.* (2007). They found that chitinase activity was lower than that in the case of non-controlled pH. They referred this behavior to the ability of the microbe to adjust itself to the environment during cultivation when no buffer was used. The same results were also found by Lai *et al.* (2005).

According to results, pH 7 was the optimum pH of medium with bacterial growth reached 1.96 OD_{600} . These results were supported by marine bacteria *Exiguobacterium* sp. (Balraj *et al.*, 2014) and *Marinobacter* (Fulzele *et al.*, 2011). Nevertheless, some of the group *Alphaproteobacteria* showed the growth well at pH 8.22 (Krause *et al.*, 2012). Bacteria are susceptible to the medium concentration of hydrogen ions, so pH change observed during the growth of bacteria also impacts the

stability of the product during fermentation. Different microbes have distinct optimal pH. Increase and decrease the pH in a medium can affect growth in bacteria.

Figure 13 Effect of initial pH of the medium on chitinase production and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

4.6.8 Effect of incubation time on chitinase production

The effect of incubation time of culture medium (24, 48, 72, 96, 120, 144, and 168 h) on chitinase production and bacterial growth was investigated. The result was present in Figure 14. In our study, there was very less chitinase activity at the first 24 h (2.22 U/mL/h) and 48 h (4.33U/mL/h), then significantly increased at 72 h (6.52 U/mL/h) or yield was 2.94-fold. After that, the chitinase production gradually decreased. It was found that chitinase production by *Bacillus* sp. B26 was increased of 2.83-fold as compared to the unoptimized basal medium with squid pen powder as a substrate.

Bacterial growth was rapidly reaching a peak at 72 h incubation about 1.90 OD₆₀₀ ($p < 0.05$). It has been shown that several *Bacillus* strains produce maximum

chitinase after three days of incubation. These include *Bacillus* sp. HU1 isolated from hot spring (Dai *et al.*, 2011), *Bacillus* sp. NCTU2 (Wen *et al.*, 2002), and *Bacillus* sp. 13.26 (Yuli *et al.*, 2004).

Figure 14 Effect of incubation time on chitinase production and growth of *Bacillus* sp. B26 under SmF. Each value is the mean of three replications. Error bars represent standard deviation.

4.7 Antifungal activity of crude chitinase after the optimized condition

Previous studies had demonstrated that chitinase activity was one of the significant factors for the killing of the fungal pathogen in the antagonistic analysis (Cornelissen and Melchers, 1993; Hebbar *et al.*, 1992; and Jach *et al.*, 1995). In this present study, the antifungal activity of chitinase was tested against nine different pathogenic fungi. Among the nine fungal pathogens tested, the chitinase showed inhibitory activity against *Fusarium solani* TISTR 3436 and *Penicillium chrysogenum* TISTR 3554 with a percentage of 83.39 and 80.12, respectively (Table 21).

Table 21 Antagonistic activity of crude chitinase after optimization against pathogenic fungi

Pathogenic fungi	Percentage of inhibition
<i>Alternaria alternata</i> TISTR 3435	0
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> TISTR 3041	0
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> TISTR 3108	0
<i>Aspergillus niger</i> TISTR 3130	0
<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i> TISTR 3285	8.67±5.86
<i>Fusarium solani</i> TISTR 3436	83.39± 1.53
<i>Mucor ruber</i> TISTR 3006	4.64±1.53
<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i> TISTR 3554	80.12±2.0
<i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i> TISTR 3016	0

However, in control well, the same volume of 5-min boiled, could not inhibit the mycelium growth of fungi (Figure 15). Several studies have demonstrated that *Bacillus subtilis* chitinases can inhibit the hyphae of *Penicillium* sp. (Karunya *et al.*, 2011). *Bacillus cereus* (Chang *et al.*, 2003) and *Bacillus* sp. DAU101 (Zarei *et al.*, 2011) inhibited the growth of *Fusarium* (wilt disease).

Figure 15 Antifungal activity of chitinase produced by *Bacillus* sp. B26 against (A) *Fusarium solani* TISTR 3436 and (B) *Penicillium chrysogenum* TISTR 3554. (1) 5-min-boiled crude chitinase, (2) 2 µg/mL of amphotericin B (3) Crude chitinase, and (4) uninoculated crude enzyme.

The chitin has been a variable form of structure in the natural source, and they exist the specific properties (Aranaz *et al.*, 2009; Van de Velde and Kiekens, 2004). This fungal cell wall has the structure of the chitin that is the same as the occurrence in other organisms. However, the fact that fungal chitin is associated with other polysaccharides that do not occur in the arthropod exoskeleton and results in a significant difference (Steinbüchel *et al.*, 2002). The difference in chitinolytic capacity caused by its binding cleft that results from the subsite structure (Sasaki *et al.*, 2002). This can have implied why the antifungal activity of *Bacillus* sp. B26 chitinase had not found and shown significantly.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

Chitinases are chitin-degrading enzymes having important physiological functions and immense potential applications. The present study described the screening of chitinolytic *Bacillus* spp. isolated from marine samples, identification of the potential isolate, optimization of chitinase production, and evaluation of the antifungal activity of crude chitinase against fungi. The results obtained were concluded as follows:

1) The chitinase producing bacteria were screened on colloidal chitin medium agar plates. From the results of testing about the chitinolytic index, 17% of tested bacterial isolates were chitinolytic bacteria. There were 14 from 83 isolates with clear of inhibition occurrence. Among this, *Bacillus* sp. B26 was selected as the best chitinase producer.

2) *Bacillus* sp. B26 is a gram-positive and spore-forming rod. It showed positive results for urease production, catalase test, starch hydrolysis, and casein hydrolysis. It exhibited negative results for citrate utilization, oxidase test, and Voges- Proskauer reaction. It produced acids from the fermentation of arabinose, lactose, maltose, glucose, sucrose, galactose, mannitol, and fructose. *Bacillus* sp. B26 could grow in medium containing 0-5 % NaCl with optimum at 2% NaCl, pH 7-8, at 37°C. *Bacillus* sp. B26 showed a 99.9% similarity to *B. paramycoides* based on the 16S rRNA sequencing.

3) The medium composition for the highest chitinase production by *Bacillus* sp. B26 was optimized. It was found that the optimized medium was composed of 2% of squid pen powder, 0.5% of sodium nitrate as the best additional nitrogen source and 2% of NaCl in the basal medium containing 0.05% of yeast extract, 0.1% of (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.03% of MgSO₄•7H₂O and 0.136% of KH₂PO₄ with an initial medium pH of 7. Under these conditions, *Bacillus* sp. B26 produced a maximum chitinase activity of 6.52 U/mL/h after 72 h of incubation. The yield of 2.83-fold was observed as compared to the unoptimized basal medium with squid pen powder as a substrate.

4) Antifungal activity of crude chitinase produced by *Bacillus* sp. B26 was tested against fungal strains including *Alternaria alternata* TISTR 3435, *Aspergillus flavus* TISTR 3041, *Aspergillus fumigatus* TISTR 3108, *Aspergillus niger* TISTR 3130, *Cladosporium cladosporioides* TISTR 3285, *Fusarium solani* TISTR 3436, *Mucor ruber* TISTR 3006, *Penicillium chrysogenum* TISTR 3554, and *Rhizopus stolonifer* TISTR 3016. It was found that the crude chitinase was more effective in inhibiting the growth of *F. solani* TISTR 3436 (83.39%) and *P. chrysogenum* TISTR 3554 (80.12%).

Chitinase produced by *B. paramycoides* B26 represents a new source for biotechnological and agricultural use. Therefore, *Bacillus* sp. B26 that produces chitinase with squid pen powder as the sole carbon source cannot only solve environmental problems but can also decrease the production costs of microbial chitinase.

5.2 Recommendation

1. Chitinase from *Bacillus* sp. B26, which has antifungal activity against *Fusarium solani* and *Penicillium chrysogenum* is expected to be used in agriculture as a biocontrol agent. Therefore, field testing of chitinase from *Bacillus* sp. B26 should be studied.
2. Chitinase production by *Bacillus* sp. B26 should be carried out using solid-state fermentation (SSF). SSF has emerged as an appropriate technology for the management of agro-industrial residues and for their value addition. SSF is a promising technology for the development of several bioprocesses and products, including the production of industrial enzymes on large-scale. Different types of substrates have been tried for the production of chitinase, which included agricultural residues.
3. Bioactive compounds produced by *Bacillus paramycoides* B26 should be investigated.

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APPENDIX A

Microbial culture media

1. Colloidal chitin medium agar (Chandrasekaran *et al.*, 2012)

Compositions (g/L)	Chitin	10
	Yeast extract	0.5
	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	1.0
	MgSO ₄ •7H ₂ O	0.3
	KH ₂ PO ₄	1.36
	NaCl	30
	Agar	15
	Distilled water	1 L

Adjusted pH at 7 and sterilization was performed by autoclave at 121°C for 15 min

2. Colloidal chitin medium broth (Chandrasekaran *et al.*, 2012)

Compositions (g/L)	Chitin	10
	Yeast extract	0.5
	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	1.0
	MgSO ₄ •7H ₂ O	0.3
	KH ₂ PO ₄	1.36
	NaCl	30
	Distilled water	1 L

Adjusted pH at 7 and sterilization was performed by autoclave at 121°C for 15 min.

3. Simmons citrate agar (Himedia) (g/L)

Magnesium sulphate	0.2
Ammonium dihydrogen phosphate	1
Dipotassium phosphate	1
Sodium citrate	2
Sodium chloride	5
Bromothymol blue	0.08
Agar	15
Distilled water	1 L

Adjusted pH at 6.8 and sterilization was performed by autoclave at 121°C for 15 min.

4. Urease medium (g/L) (Himedia)

Pepton	1.0
Glucose	1.0
NaCl	5.0
Disodium hydrogen phosphate	1.2
Potassium dihydrogen phosphate	0.8
Phenol red	0.004
Distilled water	1 L

Adjusted pH at 6.8 and sterilization was performed by autoclave at 121°C for 15 min.

5. Skim milk agar (g/L)

SM powder	28
Tryptone	5
Yeast extract	2.5
Dextrose (Glucose)	1
Agar	15
Distilled water	1 L

Adjusted pH at 6.7 and sterilization was performed by autoclave at 121°C for 15 min.

6. MR-VP broth (Himedia)

Peptone	7
Dextrose	5
Dipotassium phosphate	5
Distilled water	1 L

Final pH at 6.9 and sterilization was performed by autoclave at 121°C for 15 min.

7. Starch agar medium (g/L) (Himedia)

Meat Extract	3
Peptone	5
Starch	2
Agar	15
Distilled water	1 L

Final pH at 7.2 and sterilization was performed by autoclave at 121°C for 15 min.

8. Carbohydrate fermentation medium (g/L)

Peptone	10
Carbohydrate	5
Sodium chloride	15
Phenol red	0.018
Distilled water	1 L

Final pH at 7.2 and sterilization was performed by autoclave at 121°C for 15 min.

APPENDIX B

Methodology/Reagents/Chemicals

1. Morphological test of *Bacillus* sp. B26 (Barrow and Feltham, 2004)

1.1 Test of Gram staining

The loop was sterilized and then waited until it was cold. The *Bacillus* sp B26 inoculum was taken from the media and spread over the clean glass slide. Let it dry. Violet crystal was dropped by 2-3 drops and left for 1 minute. Glass slide was dropped with flow distilled water and dried. Lugol was dropped and left for 1 minute then washed with running water and dried. 95% alcohol given for 30 seconds, then washed with running water and dried. Safranin given for 20 seconds then washed with running water and dried. Glass slide was observed using a microscope with 10 x 100 magnification. Gram-positive bacteria showed blue or violet and gram-negative bacteria showed red.

1.2 Endospore staining

A thin smear of *Bacillus* sp. B26 inoculum was made on a clean glass slide. Air-dried and heat-fixed. Smear was covered with malachite green. The slide was steamed for 5 minutes by adding more stain to the smear for time to time. The slide was washed slowly under tap water. Again the smear was covered with safranin for 30 sec. Smear was washed with distilled water and air-dried. The glass slide was observed under the microscope. Endospores was observed under microscope with green color and parent cells was observed with red color.

2. Physiological test of bacteria (Barrow and Feltham, 2004) with modification

2.1 Citrate utilization test

Bacillus sp. B26 inoculum was inoculated by stab on the Simmon Citrate Agar (SCA) medium and incubated at 30°C for 24 hours then observed the microbial growth. Uninoculated Simmons citrate agar used as a control. Changes in the medium from green to blue indicated a positive citrate test.

2.2 Catalase test

The Catalase test was carried out by dripping 3% of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) in clean glass objects. *Bacillus* sp. B26 inoculum was applied to the glass of the object

that has been pressed with hydrogen peroxide with a loop. The suspension was mixed slowly using a loop, positive results are indicated by the formation of air bubbles.

2.3 Oxidase test

The filter paper was dropped with tetramethyl-p-phenylenediamine dihydrochloride. The isolate was picked with loop and smear in the filter paper. The inoculate was observed in the area of paper for a color change to deep blue or purple within 10-30 seconds. Positive was developed of dark purple color within 10 seconds otherwise the negative control was absence of color.

2.4 Carbohydrate fermentation

The fermentation medium was prepared with specific carbohydrate example arabinose, fructose, mannitol, galactose, sucrose, glucose, maltose, and lactose. The media was sterilized using autoclave at 15 lb pressure for 15 minutes. Types of sugars fermentation broth were inoculated with test isolate and one uninoculated tube with each fermentation broth was kept as a comparative control. Incubate tubes at 30°C for 24 hours. Positive: After incubation, the liquid in the tube was turned yellow. If negative, the tube containing medium was remained red color.

2.5 Voges-Proskauer test

Bacillus sp. B26 inoculum was inoculated into MR/VP broth. The MR/VP broth without inoculum used as a control. *Bacillus* sp. B26 inoculum was incubated for 24 hours at 30°C. After incubation, 1 mL of broth moved to a sterile test tube. Add 0.6mL of 5% α -naphthol followed by 0.2 mL of 40% KOH. The tube was shaken gently to expose the medium to atmospheric oxygen and the tube allowed to remain undisturbed for 10 to 15 minutes. A positive test was represented by the development of a red color 15 minutes

2.6 Starch hydrolysis test

Starch agar was prepared and sterilized using autoclave at 15 lbs for 15 minutes. The media was poured into a plate and allowed to solidify. The test isolate was inoculated onto the plate with a sterile transfer loop. The plate was incubated at 30°C for 48 h. After incubation, the plate was flooded with iodine. A positive test was represented by a clear of inhibition around the line of growth. A negative test was represented purple or black coloration of the medium.

2.7 Urease test

Urease medium was prepared and sterilized using an autoclave. The medium was inoculated with test isolate. The tubes were incubated at 30°C for 24 to 48 h. The medium was observed for color. A positive test was developed of bright pink color and negative was no color change.

2.8 Casein hydrolysis test

The isolate was inoculated in the skim milk agar plate either a straight line or a zig-zag. Incubate the plate at 30°C for 24 hours. Examine the milk agar plate cultures for the presence or absence of a clear area, surrounding the growth of each of the bacterial test. A positive test was showed a clear of inhibition around the colony and negative test was represented no clear of inhibition around the colony.

3. Physiological test of bacteria (Reddy *et al.*, 2011) with modification

3.1 Optimum pH and pH range for growth

1 loop *Bacillus* sp. B26 inoculum inoculated to 100 mL of sterile nutrient broth and incubated for 24 hours at 30°C. The sample was measured at OD 600 nm and adjusted the final OD at 0.5. 0.5 mL of inoculum was transferred to 5 mL of sterile nutrient broth with various pH (5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12) then incubated for 24 hours at 30°C. Nutrient broth without inoculum used as control. Bacterial growth with various pH was labeled based on OD₆₀₀. Symbol of (++++) = highest growth (>1 OD₆₀₀), (++) = good growth (0.5 - 1 OD₆₀₀), (+) = average growth (0 - 0.5 OD₆₀₀), and (-) = no growth.

3.2 Optimum temperature and temperatur range for growth

1 loop of *Bacillus* sp. B26 inoculum inoculated to 100 mL of sterile nutrient broth and incubated for 24 hours at 30°C. The sample was measured at OD 600 nm and adjusted the final OD at 0.5. 0.5 mL of inoculum was transferred to 5 mL of sterile nutrient broth with various temperature (18, 22, 37, 50, and 60°C) then incubated for 24 hours at 30°C. Nutrient broth without inoculum used as control. Bacterial growth with various temperature was labeled based on OD₆₀₀. Symbol of (++++) = highest growth (>1 OD₆₀₀), (++) = good growth (0.5 - 1 OD₆₀₀), (+) = average growth (0 - 0.5 OD₆₀₀), and (-) = no growth (0 OD₆₀₀).

3.3 Optimum NaCl concentration and NaCl concentration range for growth

1 loop of *Bacillus* sp. B26 inoculum inoculated to 100 mL of sterile nutrient broth and incubated for 24 hours at 30°C. The sample was measured at OD 600 nm and adjusted the final OD at 0.5. 0.5 mL of inoculum was transferred to 5 mL of sterile

nutrient broth with various NaCl concentrations (0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, and 10) then incubated for 24 hours at 30°C. Nutrient broth without inoculum used as control. Bacterial growth with various NaCl concentration was labeled based on OD₆₀₀. Symbol of (+++) = highest growth (>1 OD₆₀₀), (++) = good growth (0.5 - 1 OD₆₀₀), (+) = average growth (0 - 0.5 OD₆₀₀), and (-) = no growth (0 OD₆₀₀).

4. Preparation of citrate phosphate buffer 7 pH (Gomori, 1955).

Stocks solutions

Reagent A: 0.1 M solution of citric acid (19.21 g in 1 L)

Reagent B: 0.2 M solution of dibasic sodium phosphate (53.65 g of Na₂HPO₄·7H₂O or 71.7 g of Na₂HPO₄·12H₂O in 1 L of distilled water)

To make the pH 5, prepared 24.3 mL of reagent A + 25.7 mL of reagent B, diluted to a total of 100 mL.

5. Preparation of Dinitrosalicylic DNS Reagent (Saqib and Whitney, 2011).

10 g of dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) and 300 g of Rochelle salt were mixed into 800 mL of 0.5 N NaOH and heated slowly until it dissolves. The solution was made up to 1.0 L of distilled water.

6. The standard curve of N-acetylglucosamine

The dilution of N-acetyl-glucosamine (NAG) solution was made in the concentration range of 0.1 to 0.5 mg/ml. 1 mL of NAG solution was mixed with 1 ml of DNS reagent. The mixture was boiled in the water bath for 5 min. The mixture was transferred to the ice bowl to rapidly cooled down and then left to room temperature. The absorbance was measured by a spectrophotometer at 540 nm. The standard curve of N acetyl glucosamine (NAG) solution was showed and the equation of the straight line was measured for chitinase activity.

Figure 16 Standard curve of N-acetylglucosamine (NAG) solution and equation of the straight line

7. DNA extraction phenol/chloroform method (Cheng and Jiang *et al.*, 2006)

- 1) 10 mL of mid- to late-log-phase culture (0.5 – 0.7 at OD₆₀₀) was transfer to a falcon tube and pellet the cells through centrifugation at 4.470 g for 10 min. Discard the supernatant.
- 2) Resuspend pellet with the DNA solution (50 mM glucose, 25 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 10 mM EDTA) and lysozyme. Incubate 37°C for 15 mins.
- 3) 8 μL of lysozyme was added, gently mix and incubated at 37°C for 60 min
- 4) 50 μL of 10% SDS (sodium dodecyl sulfate) was added, centrifuged at 17,926 g for 10 mins, mix with 1 vol phenol. Vortex and centrifuged at 17,926 g 10 min.
- 5) The supernatant was pipette and mix with 1 vol phenol:chloroform:isoamyl alcohol, vortex and centrifuged at 17,926 g
- 6) 1/10 vol of 5M ammonium acetate was added.
- 7) Chromosomal DNA was precipitated by the addition of 2 vol of cold ethanol
- 8) DNA precipitate was spoiled with sealed Pasteur pipette, wash with 70% ethanol, air dry DNA pellet.
- 9) Dissolve in TE buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 0.1 mM EDTA).

8. Extract PCR product (GF-1 AmbiClean Kit)

- 1) A DNA sample was run on agarose gel electrophoresis to confirm the DNA band
- 2) 200 μ L of buffer DB was added to a tube containing 200 μ L PCR product (invert tube)
- 3) The column was centrifuged at 14,938 g for 1 min
- 4) The column was added 650 μ L wash buffer
- 5) Centrifuged at 14,938 g for 1 min
- 6) The column was dried (1 min)
- 7) Elution (The column was transferred to a new microtube)
- 8) 30 μ L of elution buffer was added
- 9) Centrifuged at 14,938 g for 1 min
- 10) DNA was stored at 4°C

APPENDIX C

Data

Table 22 Primary screening of chitinase producing bacteria

Isolates	Colony diameter (cm)			clear of inhibition diameter (cm)			Chitinolytic Index (CI)			Average (cm)	SD
	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III		
B26	0.95	0.94	0.95	1.55	1.54	1.55	0.63	0.64	0.63	0.63	0.00
B07	0.98	0.97	0.96	1.55	1.54	1.53	0.58	0.59	0.59	0.59	0.01
B19	1.05	1.03	1.04	1.65	1.64	1.65	0.57	0.59	0.59	0.58	0.01
B10	1.08	1.04	1.05	1.61	1.55	1.52	0.49	0.49	0.45	0.48	0.02
B20	1.20	1.21	1.25	1.73	1.74	1.75	0.44	0.44	0.40	0.43	0.02
B18	1.10	1.12	1.14	1.55	1.56	1.58	0.41	0.39	0.39	0.40	0.01
B02	1.05	1.04	1.06	1.45	1.45	1.46	0.38	0.39	0.37	0.38	0.01
B01	1.10	1.13	1.12	1.50	1.53	1.54	0.36	0.35	0.38	0.36	0.01
B09	1.45	1.43	1.46	1.85	1.83	1.86	0.28	0.28	0.27	0.28	0.00
B12	1.16	1.12	1.15	1.45	1.43	1.45	0.25	0.28	0.26	0.26	0.01
B04	1.06	1.05	1.03	1.32	1.28	1.29	0.25	0.22	0.25	0.24	0.02
B13	1.10	1.14	1.11	1.30	1.34	1.31	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.00
B16	1.43	1.42	1.41	1.60	1.58	1.59	0.12	0.11	0.13	0.12	0.01
B40	1.70	1.71	1.72	1.80	1.81	1.82	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.00

Table 23 Antagonistic activity of chitinolytic bacteria against pathogenic fungi

<i>Alternaria alternata</i> TISTR 3435										
Strains	R1 (mm)			R2 (mm)			(R1-R2)/R1			%
	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	
B07	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B10	17.00	17.00	17.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	0.71	0.76	0.76	74.51
B19	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B20	17.00	17.00	17.00	17.00	17.00	17.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B26	14.00	17.00	17.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	0.64	0.71	0.71	68.49
<i>Mucor ruber</i> TISTR 3006										
Strains	R1 (mm)			R2 (mm)			(R1-R2)/R1			%
	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	
B07	14.00	14.00	14.00	14.00	14.00	14.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B10	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B19	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B20	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B26	14.00	14.00	14.00	10.00	10.00	9.00	0.29	0.29	0.36	30.95

Table 23 continued

<i>Fusarium solani</i> TISTR 3436										
Strains	R1 (mm)			R2 (mm)			(R1-R2)/R1			%
	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	
B07	16.00	16.00	16.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	0.56	0.56	0.56	56.25
B10	17.00	16.00	16.00	5.00	6.00	6.00	0.71	0.63	0.63	65.2
B19	17.00	17.00	16.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	0.65	0.65	0.63	63.97
B20	17.00	16.00	16.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	0.65	0.63	0.63	63.24
B26	16.00	17.00	16.00	4.00	6.00	5.00	0.75	0.65	0.69	69.49
<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i> TISTR 3554										
Strains	R1 (mm)			R2 (mm)			(R1-R2)/R1			%
	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	
B07	13.00	13.00	13.00	8.00	8.00	8.00	0.38	0.38	0.38	38.46
B10	14.00	14.00	14.00	8.00	8.00	8.00	0.43	0.43	0.43	42.86
B19	15.00	14.00	14.00	8.00	9.00	8.00	0.47	0.36	0.43	41.75
B20	15.00	14.00	14.00	9.00	8.00	8.00	0.40	0.43	0.43	41.90
B26	15.00	14.00	14.00	8.00	7.00	8.00	0.47	0.50	0.43	46.51

Table 23 continued

<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> TISTR 3041										
Strains	R1 (mm)			R2 (mm)			(R1-R2)/R1			%
	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	
B07	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B10	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B19	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B20	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B26	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
<i>Aspergillus niger</i> TISTR 3130										
Strains	R1 (mm)			R2 (mm)			(R1-R2)/R1			%
	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	
B07	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B10	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B19	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B20	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B26	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0

Table 23 continued

<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i> TISTR 3285										
Strains	R1 (mm)			R2 (mm)			(R1-R2)/R1			%
	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	
B07	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B10	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B19	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B20	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B26	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
<i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i> TISTR 3016										
Strains	R1 (mm)			R2 (mm)			(R1-R2)/R1			%
	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	
B07	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B10	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B19	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B20	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B26	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	18.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0

Table 24 Chitinase activity of *Bacillus* spp. in secondary screening

Stains	Time	Samples (OD ₅₄₀)			Control (OD ₅₄₀)	Concentration of NAG	Chitinase activity (U/mL/h)
		I	II	III			
B07	day 1	0.105	0.103	0.107	0.105	0.081	0.732
	day 2	0.104	0.109	0.106	0.106	0.082	0.738
	day 3	0.099	0.099	0.119	0.106	0.081	0.735
	day 4	0.106	0.098	0.112	0.105	0.081	0.733
	day 5	0.107	0.109	0.1	0.105	0.081	0.733
B10	day 1	0.103	0.103	0.088	0.098	0.077	0.698
	day 2	0.096	0.106	0.098	0.100	0.078	0.708
	day 3	0.103	0.104	0.102	0.103	0.080	0.722
	day 4	0.103	0.105	0.1	0.103	0.080	0.721
	day 5	0.109	0.103	0.094	0.102	0.079	0.717
B19	day 1	0.1	0.105	0.104	0.103	0.081	0.722
	day 2	0.109	0.102	0.108	0.106	0.082	0.738
	day 3	0.106	0.102	0.113	0.107	0.082	0.742
	day 4	0.104	0.103	0.11	0.106	0.081	0.735
	day 5	0.108	0.107	0.102	0.106	0.081	0.735
B20	day 1	0.089	0.1	0.096	0.095	0.076	0.683
	day 2	0.098	0.096	0.109	0.101	0.079	0.712
	day 3	0.121	0.115	0.089	0.108	0.083	0.748
	day 4	0.103	0.105	0.109	0.106	0.081	0.735
	day 5	0.107	0.1	0.1	0.102	0.080	0.719

Table 24 continued

Stains	Time	Samples (OD ₅₄₀)			Control (OD ₅₄₀)	Concentration of NAG	Chitinase activity (U/mL/h)
		I	II	III			
B26	day 1	0.108	0.109	0.104	0.107	0.082	0.742
	day 2	0.112	0.107	0.105	0.108	0.083	0.746
	day 3	0.108	0.109	0.111	0.109	0.083	0.753
	day 4	0.107	0.109	0.11	0.109	0.083	0.750
	day 5	0.105	0.107	0.112	0.108	0.083	0.746

Table 25 Antifungal activity of crude chitinase of *Bacillus* sp. B26 against pathogenic fungi

Pathogenic fungi	R1 (mm)			R2 (mm)			(R1-R2)/R1			%	SD
	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III		
<i>Fusarium solani</i>	12.00	13.00	12.90	7.00	7.00	7.00	0.42	0.46	0.46	44.52	0.02
<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	14.00	14.00	15.00	9.00	10.00	9.00	0.36	0.29	0.40	34.76	0.06
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	14.00	14.00	14.00	14.00	14.00	14.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0	0.00
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0	0.00
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0	0.00
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0	0.00
<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i>	14.00	14.00	14.00	14.00	14.00	14.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0	0.00
<i>Mucor ruber</i>	14.00	14.00	14.00	14.00	14.00	14.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0	0.00
<i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i>	17.00	17.00	17.00	17.00	17.00	17.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0	0.00

R1 is the growth of the fungus measured from the center of the fungal colony to direction away from the bacterial streaks (mm).

R2 is the growth of the fungus measured from the center of the fungal colony towards the bacterial streaks (mm).

Table 26 Effect of chitin source on chitinase production by *Bacillus* sp. B26

Chitin source (1%)	Samples (OD ₅₄₀)			Control (OD ₅₄₀)	Concentration NAG			Chitinase activity (U/mL/h)			Average (U/mL/h)	SD
	I	II	III		I	II	III	I	II	III		
Colloidal chitin	0.153	0.157	0.135	0.004	0.105	0.108	0.096	0.953	0.975	0.867	0.932	0.058
Shrimp shell powder	0.305	0.278	0.293	0.008	0.185	0.171	0.179	1.674	1.545	1.618	1.613	0.065
Squid pens powder	0.423	0.434	0.438	0.006	0.250	0.255	0.258	2.257	2.310	2.330	2.299	0.038
Crab shell powder	0.162	0.173	0.170	0.006	0.109	0.115	0.114	0.989	1.044	1.029	1.021	0.029

Table 27 Effect of chitin source concentration on chitinase production by *Bacillus* sp. B26

Squid pen powder source (%)	Samples (OD ₅₄₀)			Control (OD ₅₄₀)	Concentration NAG			Chitinase activity (U/mL)			Average (U/mL)	SD
	I	II	III		I	II	III	I	II	III		
0.5	0.254	0.249	0.267	0.013	0.155	0.152	0.162	1.401	1.378	1.463	1.414	0.044
1	0.475	0.476	0.470	0.019	0.271	0.271	0.268	2.452	2.454	2.426	2.444	0.016
2	0.625	0.661	0.690	0.012	0.355	0.375	0.390	3.213	3.387	3.525	3.375	0.156
3	0.604	0.656	0.705	0.012	0.344	0.372	0.398	3.106	3.359	3.601	3.355	0.248

Table 28 Effect of additional carbon source on chitinase production by *Bacillus* sp. B26

Additional carbon source (1%)	Samples (OD ₅₄₀)			Control (OD ₅₄₀)	Concentration of NAG			Chitinase activity (U/mL)			Average (U/mL)	SD
	I	II	III		I	II	III	I	II	III		
Without additional carbon	0.74	0.73	0.72	0.027	0.41	0.402	0.397	3.708	3.635	3.591	3.645	0.059
Nag	0.67	0.66	0.68	0.632	0.044	0.04	0.049	2.808	2.502	3.115	2.808	0.306
Glucose	0.71	0.71	0.72	0.669	0.048	0.047	0.052	3.047	2.979	3.319	3.115	0.180
Lactose	0.75	0.74	0.75	0.695	0.053	0.050	0.056	3.353	3.183	3.523	3.353	0.170
Maltose	0.66	0.69	0.67	0.642	0.037	0.051	0.043	2.366	3.217	2.706	2.763	0.428

Table 29 Effect of nitrogen source on chitinase production by *Bacillus* sp. B26

Nitrogen source (1%)	Samples (OD ₅₄₀)			Control (OD ₅₄₀)	Concentration of NAG			Chitinase activity (U/mL)			Average (U/mL)	SD
	I	II	III		I	II	III	I	II	III		
Control	0.664	0.589	0.721	0.005	0.380	0.340	0.411	3.437	3.075	3.714	3.409	0.320
Yeast extract	0.760	0.756	0.795	0.569	0.128	0.126	0.147	1.162	1.138	1.330	1.210	0.105
Peptone	0.272	0.230	0.283	0.020	0.161	0.138	0.167	1.455	1.250	1.507	1.404	0.136
NaNO ₃	0.443	0.413	0.453	0.004	0.262	0.246	0.267	4.732	4.440	4.829	4.667	0.202
NH ₄ NO ₃	0.725	0.756	0.684	0.002	0.414	0.431	0.392	3.747	3.896	3.546	3.730	0.176

Table 30 Effect of nitrogen source concentration on chitinase production by *Bacillus* sp. B26

NaNO ₃ concentration (%)	Samples (OD ₅₄₀)			Control	Concentration of NAG			Chitinase activity (U/ml)			Average (U/mL)	SD
	I	II	III		I	II	III	I	II	III		
0.5	0.447	0.449	0.453	0.013	0.259	0.260	0.262	4.683	4.704	4.741	4.710	0.030
1	0.451	0.422	0.439	0.011	0.262	0.246	0.256	4.743	4.455	4.626	4.608	0.145
2	0.764	0.759	0.781	0.010	0.431	0.429	0.440	3.899	3.878	3.982	3.919	0.055
3	0.705	0.754	0.721	0.009	0.400	0.427	0.409	3.617	3.856	3.695	3.723	0.122

Table 31 Effect of NaCl concentration on chitinase production by *Bacillus* sp. B26

NaCl concentration (%)	Samples (OD ₅₄₀)			Control (OD ₅₄₀)	Concentration of NAG			Chitinase activity (U/mL)			Average (U/mL)	SD
	I	II	III		I	II	III	I	II	III		
0	0.291	0.303	0.296	0.001	0.181	0.188	0.184	1.641	1.697	1.663	1.667	0.028
1	0.273	0.278	0.282	0.003	0.171	0.173	0.176	3.088	3.133	3.179	3.133	0.046
2	0.423	0.386	0.360	0.003	0.251	0.232	0.218	6.819	6.279	5.908	6.335	0.458
3	0.265	0.312	0.257	0.001	0.168	0.193	0.163	4.549	5.228	4.433	4.736	0.429
4	0.331	0.331	0.440	0.002	0.202	0.203	0.261	3.661	3.665	4.720	4.015	0.611

Table 32 Effect of initial pH of the medium on chitinase production by *Bacillus* sp. B26

Initial pH	Samples (OD ₅₄₀)			Control (OD ₅₄₀)	Concentration of NAG			Chitinase activity (U/mL)			Average (U/mL)	SD
	I	II	III		I	II	III	I	II	III		
5.0	0.231	0.243	0.225	0.002	0.149	0.155	0.145	4.034	4.202	3.946	4.061	0.130
6.0	0.309	0.315	0.302	0.002	0.191	0.194	0.187	5.172	5.259	5.070	5.167	0.095
7.0	0.403	0.386	0.369	0.002	0.241	0.232	0.223	6.542	6.294	6.053	6.296	0.244
8.0	0.313	0.322	0.323	0.002	0.193	0.198	0.198	5.230	5.358	5.376	5.321	0.080
9.0	0.240	0.221	0.212	0.002	0.153	0.143	0.138	4.164	3.888	3.757	3.936	0.208

Table 33 Effect of incubation on chitinase production by *Bacillus* sp. B26

Incubation time (days)	Samples (OD ₅₄₀)			Control (OD ₅₄₀)	Concentration of NAG			Chitinase activity (U/mL)			Average (U/mL)	SD
	I	II	III		I	II	III	I	II	III		
1	0.411	0.414	0.409	0.002	0.246	0.247	0.244	2.220	2.235	2.210	2.222	0.012
2	0.399	0.400	0.400	0.002	0.239	0.240	0.240	4.323	4.333	4.333	4.330	0.006
3	0.403	0.400	0.402	0.002	0.241	0.240	0.241	6.543	6.499	6.528	6.524	0.022
4	0.388	0.389	0.389	0.002	0.233	0.234	0.234	6.324	6.339	6.339	6.334	0.008
5	0.554	0.554	0.555	0.002	0.322	0.322	0.323	5.831	5.831	5.840	5.834	0.006
6	0.453	0.451	0.451	0.002	0.268	0.267	0.267	4.848	4.829	4.829	4.835	0.011
7	0.595	0.595	0.594	0.002	0.344	0.344	0.344	3.115	3.115	3.110	3.113	0.003

Table 34 Antifungal activity of optimization crude chitinase of *Bacillus* sp. B26

Pathogenic fungi	R1 (mm)			R2 (mm)			(R1-R2)/R1			%	SD
	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III		
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	22.00	22.00	22.00	22.00	22.00	22.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	28.00	27.00	27.00	28.00	27.00	27.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	29.00	29.00	29.00	29.00	29.00	29.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i>	26.90	26.40	23.50	24.00	23.00	23.00	0.11	0.13	0.02	8.60	0.06
<i>Fusarium solani</i>	25.90	23.80	23.90	4.00	4.20	4.00	0.85	0.82	0.83	83.39	0.02
<i>Mucor ruber</i>	26.00	25.00	24.00	24.00	23.90	23.60	0.08	0.04	0.02	4.59	0.03
<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	25.00	23.20	22.10	5.00	5.00	4.00	0.80	0.78	0.82	80.12	0.02
<i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i>	28.00	27.00	27.00	28.00	27.00	27.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

R1 is the fungal growth radius distance (mm) measured from the center of the fungal colony towards the negative control well and

R2 is the fungal growth radius distance (mm) towards the sample well.

Sequence data of *Bacillus paramyoides*

AAAAAATATGAGCTACACTGTTATCTAGTTTTCAAAGAACATACATTTATA
TATGAGAGATAGTTCTCTCAAACTGAACAAAACGAAACACGGAACTTA
TATTGATGAACAGCGTTCATCAATTCTCCATAGAAAGGAGGTGATCCAGC
CGCACCTTCCGATACGGCTACCTTGTTACGACTTCACCCCAATCATCTGTC
CCACCTTAGGCGGCTGGCTCCATAAAGGTTACCCACCGACTTCGGGTGTT
ACAAACTCTCGTGGTGTGACGGGCGGTGTGTACAAGGCCCGGGAACGTAT
TCACCGCGGCATGCTGATCCGCGATTACTAGCGATTCCAGCTTCATGTAGG
CGAGTTGCAGCCTACAATCCGAACCTGAGAACGGTTTTATGAGATTAGCTC
CACCTCGCGGTCTTGCAGCTCTTTGTACCGTCCATTGTAGCACGTGTGTAG
CCCAGGTCATAAGGGGCATGATGATTTGACGTCATCCCCACCTTCCTCCGG
TTTGTACCGGCAGTCACCTTAGAGTGCCCAACTTAATGATGGCAACTAA
GATCAAGGGTTGCGCTCGTTGCGGGACTTAACCCAACATCTCACGACACG
AGCTGACGACAACCATGCACCACCTGTCACTCTGCTCCCGAAGGAGAAGC
CCTATCTCTAGGGTTGTCAGAGGATGTCAAGACCTGGTAAGGTTCTTCGCG
TTGCTTCGAATTAAACCACATGCTCCACCGCTTGTGCGGGCCCCCGTCAAT
TCCTTTGAGTTTCAGCCTTGCGGCCGTACTCCCCAGGCGGAGTGCTTAATG
CGTTAACTTCAGCACTAAAGGGCGGAAACCCTCTAACACTTAGCACTCAT
CGTTTACGGCGTGGACTACCAGGGTATCTAATCCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCT
TTCGCGCCTCAGTGTCAGTTACAGACCAGAAAGTCGCCTTCGCCACTGGT
GTTCTCCATATCTCTACGCATTTACCGCTACACATGGAATTCCACTTTC
CTCTTCTGCACTCAAGTCTCCAGTTTCCAATGACCCTCCACGGTTGAGCC
GTGGGCTTTTACATCAGACTTAAGAAACCACCTGCGCGCGCTTTACGCC
AATAATTCCGGATAACGCTTGCCACCTACGTATTACCGCGGCTGCTGGCA
CGTAGTTAGCCGTGGCTTTCTGGTTAGGTACCGTCAAGGTGCCAGCTTATT
CAACTAGCACTTGTTCTTCCCTAACAACAGAGTTTTACGACCCGAAAGCCT
TCATCACTCACGCGGCGTTGCTCCGTCAGACTTTCGTCCATTGCGGAAGAT
TCCCTACTGCTGCCTCCCGTAGGAGTCTGGGCCGTGTCTCAGTCCCAGTGT
GGCCGATCACCTCTCAGGTCGGCTACGCATCGTTGCCTTGGTGAGCCGTT
ACCTACCAACTAGCTAATGCGACGCGGGTCCATCCATAAGTGACAGCCG
AAGCCGCCTTTCAATTTTGAACCATGCGGTTCAAATGTTATCCGGTATTA
GCCCCGGTTTCCCGGAGTTATCCCAGTCTTATGGGCAGGTTACCCACGTGT

TACTCACCCGTCCGCCGCTAACTTCATAAGAGCAAGCTCTTAATCCATTCG
CTCGACTTGCATGTATTAGGCACGCCGCCAGCGTTCATCCTGAGCCAGGA
TCAAACCTCTCCAATAAAGTTAGTTTGTCTAGCATCTAAAA

VITAE

Name **Edy Kurniawan**

Student ID **5920320501**

Educational Attainment

Degree	Name of institution	Year of graduation
Bachelor in biology education	State University of Makassar, Indonesia	2015

Scholarship Awards during Enrolment

1. Thailand's Education Hub for ASEAN Countries (TEH-AC) scholarship 2016 by PSU
2. Graduate School Dissertation Funding for Thesis 2017 by PSU

List of Publication and Proceeding

- Kurniawan, E, Panphon, S. and Leelakriangsak, M. 2018. Screening of chitinase producing *Bacillus* sp. and antifungal activity against phytopathogenic fungi. International Conference on Multidisciplinary Contemporary Research (ICMCR) 2018, Getting highland, Malaysia, 24 – 25 February 2018. (Oral presentation with abstract).
- Kurniawan, E, Panphon, S. and Leelakriangsak, M. 2018. Antagonistic activity of chitinolytic bacteria isolated from marine samples against phytopathogenic fungi. The 23rd seminar and the 12th congress of Indonesia society for biochemistry and molecular biology in conjunction with the 2nd International conference. UNAIR, Surabaya, Indonesia, 11-12 October 2018 (Oral presentation with abstract)
- Kurniawan, E, Panphon, S. and Leelakriangsak, M. 2019. Potential of marine chitinolytic *Bacillus* isolates as biocontrol agents of phytopathogenic fungi. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science. 217 (1), 012044. (5 pages).